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Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **G**rape, **O**Live and **D**urum wheat food systems

D1.4

Mapping uncertainty and skill in seasonal forecasts and climate data

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The skill of seasonal forecasts of temperature and precipitation globally, and over Europe and Colombia were assessed. The forecasts had good skill for temperature in both locations. The skill for precipitation over Europe was low, but was notably better over Colombia.

A subset of the EURO-CORDEX regional climate model ensemble was identified. Climate simulations from this subset were compared with the E-OBS gridded dataset for the whole Mediterranean area, and a more in-depth analysis was performed for the MED-GOLD study regions. The analysis focused on key climatic variables (temperature and precipitation), as well as other derived indices (numbers of hot days and nights, numbers of wet and dry days). Overall, the models reproduced the large-scale observed features, but some biases in the simulations were evident. Calibration of the model data significantly reduced the sizes of the biases.

All of the climate models projected increases in temperature and numbers of hot days and nights over the MED-GOLD study regions. Reductions in precipitation were projected in spring, summer, and autumn, but some of the changes were not significant until later in the twenty-first century.

A small number of simulations from the Central American regional climate model ensemble (CAM-CORDEX) were assessed using the AgMERRA dataset. Large biases in the modelled data were identified, which largely originate from the GCMs used to drive the RCMs. A different method to that used with the EURO-CORDEX data was used to calibrate the climate model data for Colombia. The benefit of the calibration is demonstrated, by comparing projections of temperature and precipitation over Colombia in raw and calibrated data.

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, Part B Table1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	X
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	X
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. PURPOSE

The purpose of this report is to assess the climate forecast skill of seasonal predictions and fidelity of longer term climate projections over the MED-GOLD study regions. These assessments focus on Essential Climate Variables; simulations of climatic indicators for the three crop types will be assessed separately in work packages 2, 3 and 4. Guidance will be provided on which meteorological variables are simulated most accurately by seasonal forecasts and climate model simulations. Locations with high skill in seasonal forecasts will be identified, with a focus on the three key MED-GOLD study regions. The results will feed into work packages 2, 3 and 4, for the development and testing of the climate service tools.

1.2. SCOPE

Seasonal forecasts from three different modelling centres were selected for analysis. The models used to generate these forecasts have been recently upgraded, and initial tests by the providers show clear improvements in the forecasts over the previous versions. Climate projections from the CORDEX initiative were selected, as they are readily available, have reasonably high spatial resolutions, and (at least for Europe) a wide range of regional model simulations are available. This report focuses on essential climate variables, specifically temperature and precipitation. Climatic indices for each of the three crop types will be assessed separately within WPs 2, 3 and 4.

1.3. DEFINITIONS AND ACRONYMS

1.3.1. DEFINITIONS

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1-1: Definitions

Concept / Term	Definition
Bias	The error(s) in simulations of climate by models, when compared with observations.
Bias-adjustment	A collective term for statistical methods applied to climate model data to reduce the biases. Also called bias correction.
Calibration	The act of reducing the magnitude of the bias in climate model simulations.
Climatology	A long-term average of one or more meteorological variables for a given location, typically calculated over 20 or 30 years. The climatology can be calculated on daily, monthly, seasonal or annual timescales.
Downscaling	Methods for creating climate information at higher spatial and/or temporal scales from coarser resolution simulations. Dynamical and/or statistical methods may be used.
Essential Climate Variables	A group of variables that critically contributes to the characterization of Earth's climate. For the surface, the variables include air temperature, precipitation, humidity, wind speed and direction, solar radiation and surface air pressure.
Grid box or Grid cell	Most climate models divide the atmosphere up into a series of points on a regular grid, and simulate the climate at each point. The grid is three-dimensional, hence the volume around each point forms a box, commonly referred to as either a 'grid box' or a 'grid cell'.
Observations	Measurements of meteorological variables made by surface weather stations or satellites. These measurements can be interpolated to create gridded sets of climate information which are used for evaluation of seasonal forecasts and climate model simulations; the gridded datasets are also referred to as observations.
Prediction	A prediction, such as a weather or seasonal forecast, is an estimate of actual future conditions based on knowledge of the present state of the climate. Currently, predictions can range from hours to a few years ahead.
Projection	Climate projections are estimates of future climatic conditions under assumptions of future emissions of greenhouse gases, changes in land use, and many other factors. Climate projections are created using scenarios of possible future human activity, which include greenhouse gas emissions and land use change.
Resolution	Relates to the spatial resolution of the grids used by climate models and some observational datasets. The resolution may be given in degrees or km. High resolution refers to a grid spacing less than 0.44° (about 50 km); Low resolution grids have a spacing of 1° or greater, or distances larger than about 100 km.

Concept / Term	Definition
Skill	A statistical measure of the accuracy of seasonal forecasts.
Verification	The process of assessing the quality of a forecast.

1.3.2. ACRONYMS

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1-2: Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
AgMERRA	A climate dataset for agricultural modelling, created by adjusting the MERRA reanalysis with surface observations and satellite data.
CAM44	Central American CORDEX regional climate model simulations executed at a resolution of 0.44° (about 50 km)
CMIP3	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 3
CMIP5	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5
CORDEX	Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment
E-OBS	European daily high-resolution gridded dataset
ECVs	Essential Climate Variables
ETCCDI	Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices
EUR11	European (EURO-CORDEX) regional climate model simulations executed at a resolution of 0.11° (about 12 km)
EUR44	European (EURO-CORDEX) regional climate model simulations executed at a resolution of 0.44° (about 50 km)
FNC	Federación Nacional de Cafeteros (National Federation of Coffee Growers of Colombia)
GHCN-D	Global Historical Climatology Network - Daily
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
MED11	Mediterranean (Med-CORDEX) regional climate model simulations executed at a resolution of 0.11° (about 12 km)
GCM	Global climate model
RCM	Regional climate model
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathways, which replaced the SRES scenarios, and were used to drive the CMIP5 model simulations
SRES	Special Report on Emissions Scenarios. The scenarios described in this special report are referred to as the 'SRES scenarios', and were used to drive the CMIP3 model simulations
SST	Sea Surface Temperature

2. REFERENCES

2.1. REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document. They are referenced in this document in the form [RD.x]. Articles in scientific journals and other publications are listed separately in the Bibliography.

Table 2-1: Reference Documents

Ref.	Title	Code	Version	Date
[RD.1]	Assessment of quality of European climate observations and their appropriateness for use in climate services for each sector	D1.3	1.6	29-11-2018
[RD.2]	Report on the knowledge capitalization of the olive oil sector	D2.1	1.9	25-09-2018
[RD.3]	Report on the two case studies at seasonal- and long-term timescales for the wine sector	D3.1	1.5	23-08-2018
[RD.4]	Report on the identified specific needs and opportunities	D4.1	4.0	29-11-2018

3. OBSERVATIONS

Several different sources of observations have been used to evaluate seasonal forecasts and climate simulations. Many of these datasets have been evaluated previously [RD.1], and so are only summarised briefly here.

3.1. EUROPE

E-OBS is a gridded dataset derived from surface-based weather station data, and covers the whole of Europe. Data for five meteorological variables are available: daily minimum, mean and maximum temperature, daily precipitation totals, and daily averaged sea level pressure. They cover the area 25°N - 75°N, 40°W - 75°E. More recent versions of E-OBS (v15 onwards) have benefitted from greatly increased numbers of stations in some countries (e.g., Germany, Sweden and Poland). However, the coverage of stations in and around the MED-GOLD study regions is sparse. In these regions, many more stations are present, but the data have not been made available for the European Climate Assessment Dataset, on which E-OBS is based. In this report, data from E-OBS v17 have been used. It is noted that a newer version (v19) was released during March 2019, which has a higher spatial resolution than the previous versions. However, the release was too late for use within Deliverable D1.3 [RD.1] and the present report. The assessments in D1.3 [RD.1] used v17, and most of the results shown here had already been generated before v19 was released.

Two set of observations are used to evaluate the seasonal forecasts and calibrate the climate model simulations. In the three MED-GOLD study regions (Douro valley, Portugal; Andalucía, Spain; central Italy), local weather station data are available. A comparison of these observations with E-OBS [RD.1] was satisfactory.

3.2. COLOMBIA

A gridded dataset similar to E-OBS (at the time of writing) does not exist for Colombia. It was not possible to obtain surface observations from IDEAM (the Colombian Meteorological Service). Instead, surface observations were searched for in two publicly available databases, the Global Historical Climate Network - Daily (GHCN-D) and Automated Surface Observing System (ASOS), which holds sub-daily data archived from weather stations located at airports. Only a small number of stations within Colombia were available from both datasets, and the data coverage was poor. Data from some stations in GHCN-D had good availability in the 1960s-1980s, whereas others had little data until around 2010. In ASOS, the data were only available from around 2010, and were often incomplete. For example, for some stations, data were only available for the afternoon and evening.

Owing to the issues above, the AgMERRA dataset (Ruane et al. 2015) was used in the place of surface observations. AgMERRA is a global climate dataset that provides daily continuous meteorological data for the period 1980-2010. Daily resolution data from the Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications (MERRA) have been combined with in-situ and remotely-sensed observational datasets for temperature, precipitation, and solar radiation, leading to substantial reductions in bias in comparison with a network of 2324 surface weather stations located in agricultural regions worldwide. The solar radiation data have been replaced with NASA/GEWEX surface radiation budget.

4. EVALUATION OF SEASONAL FORECASTS

4.1. INTRODUCTION

Weather forecasts provide information over periods ranging from hours to several days. While it is generally not possible to predict daily weather beyond about a week ahead, it is possible to forecast average conditions over the next few months. Seasonal forecasts provide information about these long-term averages.

A seasonal forecast consists of many individual forecasts, collectively referred to as an 'ensemble'. Each forecast begins from an observed state of the atmosphere, land and ocean. These initial conditions are not known precisely, one reason being that observing stations and instruments are sparsely distributed in some regions. The sensitivity of the forecasts to the initial conditions is taken into account by changing the starting conditions, which reflects the uncertainty in the initial state. In addition to the sensitivity to the starting conditions, forecasts can also be sensitive to the representation of the real climate system within the forecast model. This source of uncertainty can be captured by changing parameter values in the model. These techniques generate an 'ensemble' of seasonal forecasts, with each individual forecast referred to as an 'ensemble member', or simply a 'member'. Forecast products are created by analysing the output from all the ensemble members.

When making a seasonal forecast, two sets of simulations are used, called a hindcast and forecast. A hindcast is run for a previous time period (e.g., 1993-2016) and is used to calibrate the forecast by comparison with observations. The forecast predicts future conditions over the next 3-6 months. Both the hindcast and forecast consist of a number of individual ensemble members.

Agriculture is very sensitive to climate variability, extremes and the impacts of climate change. Seasonal predictions are one of the mitigation strategies available to allow the end-users to adapt their decision making, e.g. using temperature and precipitation information from one to several months into the future. Although operational seasonal predictions are issued by a number of forecast services (Shafiee-Jood et al. 2014; Weisheimer and Palmer, 2014; Buontempo et al. 2014), the agricultural sector seldom benefits from them. General Circulation Models (GCMs) suffer from substantial systematic biases in some regions and have resolutions coarser than those demanded by the end-users. In fact, agriculture decisions at these time-scales normally rely on climatology, a widespread behavior that might be linked to the tendency of decision makers to reduce the risk of losses by taking conservative decisions. This approach leads to a chronic departure from optimal management and could have important economic impacts on their activity. Consequently, the need to demonstrate the benefits of seasonal predictions in the management of agriculture offers a window of opportunity to develop novel strategies to approach the problem.

Hence, the estimation of the seasonal forecast quality based on its past performance is a fundamental step towards the construction of climate services (Doblas-Reyes et al. 2013). The benefit of the forecast can be quantified relative to other prediction methods. Thus, seasonal predictions have to be systematically compared with a reference climate (e.g., from reanalyses or observations) to assess their overall quality in a multi-faceted process known as forecast quality assessment (Mason and Baddour, 2008). Three sources of uncertainty in common scoring metrics of probabilistic predictions should be considered: improper estimates of probabilities from small-sized ensembles, insufficient number of forecast cases, and imperfect reference values due to observation errors. A way to alleviate these problems is to use several scoring measures to offer a comprehensive picture of the forecast quality of the system (Jolliffe and Stephenson, 2012) and to apply statistical inference as often as required. This information is also valuable to choose optimal bias correction and downscaling methods (Ruffault et al. 2013). Hence, this quality assessment framework seeks to provide the end-users with the tools to understand which approaches could best fit their interests.

In the present study, the calibration method of Torralba et al. (2017) is introduced to reduce biases. This technique can operate directly both on monthly and daily data and, is therefore suitable for applications demanding predicted series with high temporal and/or spatial resolution.

4.2. DATA

Monthly mean data for mean temperature, maximum temperature, minimum temperature and precipitation from the forecasts have been verified. Since the data were obtained from the Copernicus Data Store (CDS) the horizontal resolution of the data is 1 degree. The purpose of analysing different models lies in the aim of assembling a multi-model in future phases of the project. The dataset used to verify the seasonal forecasts is summarised in the next section, followed by a summary of the seasonal forecast (i.e. prediction) datasets evaluated.

4.2.1. JRA-55 REANALYSIS

The JRA-55 reanalysis (Kobayashi et al. 2015) is the second global atmospheric reanalysis supplied by the Japanese Meteorological Agency (JMA). The data are available from 1958 and are updated in real-time. It is the first global reanalysis that applies the four-dimensional variational analysis (4D-VAR) for the last half-century. Besides using the

4D-Var method, it improves on the previous reanalysis, JRA-25 (Onogi et al. 2007), by different means like the inclusion of Variational Bias correction (VarBC) for satellite radiances, a new radiation scheme or the introduction of dynamic greenhouse concentrations.

Many different reanalyses are available. The JRA55 reanalysis was selected as the reference for seasonal forecast verification because it is a state-of-the-art reanalysis - it uses a four-dimensional variational data assimilation system (4DVAR), which means the times of observations as well as their values are assimilated. JRA55 is also updated in near real-time, which is an advantage compared with other reanalyses, if in future stages of MED-GOLD the operational potential is assessed. Even though there are some differences amongst reanalysis datasets, the uncertainties linked to the choice of reanalyses tend to be smaller than those inherent to the seasonal predictions themselves. What is most important is to be consistent and use the same reference dataset to verify the different forecast models, so a comparison of performance can be made.

4.2.2. PREDICTION DATASETS

Three different seasonal forecast datasets have been evaluated. They are summarised in the following subsections.

4.2.2.1. ECMWF SYSTEM-5 (SEAS5)

SEAS5 is the fifth generation of ECMWF's seasonal forecasting system (Johnson et al., 2019). It replaces the former ECMWF System 4 (S4) and uses the Integrated Forecast System, IFS, Cycle 43r1. The re-forecast of SEAS5 covers a 36-year period, from 1981 to 2017, with an ensemble of 25 members. Compared to S4 it includes a number of enhancements in the atmospheric resolution, land-surface initialisation and in the ocean model. The operational component has 51 members and starts in 1981.

In the atmospheric component, there are 91 vertical levels (the same as S4). Regarding the land-surface initialisation, the SEAS5 includes a new offline recalculation at the native atmospheric resolution with a revised precipitation forcing. Although this initialisation is still not perfect (the reanalysis and real-time assimilation are not the same), tests performed show a good degree of consistency between the initialisation of SEAS5 re-forecast and real-time predictions. Finally, the SEAS5 uses the new version of the ocean model NEMO (Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean), with an upgraded model version, ocean physics and resolution. The ocean and sea-ice initial conditions are provided by a new ocean analysis and reanalysis ensemble (ORAS5).

4.2.2.2. MÉTÉO-FRANCE SYSTEM-6 (MF6)

Météo-France System-6 (MF6) is the sixth generation of the Météo-France long-range prediction system. The hindcast covers the period 1993-2016 and consists of an ensemble of 25 members. The operational ensemble starts from 2017 and has 51 members. The ensemble spread is generated by a stochastic dynamics technique in addition to using a lagged initialization. The atmospheric component is the Arpege-IFS which is a complex code designed not only for weather forecasts and climate simulation, but also for data assimilation and pre- and post- processing of forecasts. It has been extended, diversified and increased in complexity since 1986, jointly by Météo-France and ECMWF. The core of this Arpege model version is the cycle 37T1 which has 91 vertical levels. Regarding the land model, it uses SURFEX v8.1; whereas for the ocean, it includes Nemo v3.6 together with the ocean reanalysis ORCA.

4.2.2.3. UKMO GLOSEA5

In MED-GOLD we use the latest coupled configuration of the Met Office Unified Model for seasonal predictions (GloSea5 GC2). This is comprised of component configurations Global Atmosphere 6.0 (GA6.0), Global Land 6.0 (GL6.0), Global Ocean 5.0 (GO5.0) and Global Sea Ice 6.0 (GSI6.0). GA6.0 and GL6.0 are fully documented by Walters et al. (2015), whilst GO5.0 is described by Megann et al. (2014) and GSI6.0 by Rae et al. (2015). The re-forecast of GloSea5 covers a 36-year period, from 1981 to 2016, with an ensemble of 28 members.

Overall GC2 is shown to be an improvement on the configurations used currently, particularly in terms of modes of variability (e.g. mid-latitude and tropical cyclone intensities, the Madden-Julian Oscillation and El Niño Southern Oscillation). Relative to the previous GloSea5 GA3, GC2 has a significant revision to the atmosphere dynamical core and a number of parametrization revisions. It has additional changes including a new ocean model, new sea-ice model, new cloud scheme, and considerable revisions to all of the existing parametrization schemes. The vertical resolution is set by the component definitions, being 85 levels in the atmosphere.

4.3. METHODOLOGY

The methodology used to calibrate, and then verify the seasonal forecasts, is described in the following sections.

4.3.1. CALIBRATION

To reduce the biases associated with the predictions, calibration via bias-adjustment in cross-validation is used to correct the raw predictions obtained from SEAS5 considering the JRA-55 reanalysis as the reference dataset. The calibration method can be considered as a way of obtaining predictions with an interannual variance that is equivalent to that of a reference dataset in a similar way to the simple bias correction method but ensuring, simultaneously, an increased reliability of the probabilistic predictions. The method is sometimes referred to as climate conserving recalibration after Weigel et al. (2009). Here we consider the variance inflation EMOS method introduced in Doblus-Reyes et al. (2005). This method was used by Torralba et al. (2017) to produce reliable seasonal predictions of wind speeds. This calibration strategy has been selected because an inflation of the ensemble spread is required to obtain reliable probabilities.

If x_i is the ensemble-mean prediction for any grid point at year i and z_{ij} is the difference of the ensemble member j from the ensemble-mean in year i , then the calibrated estimate y_{ij} of the ensemble member j for year i , can be expressed as:

$$y_{ij} = \alpha x_i + \beta z_{ij}$$

The coefficients α and β are defined as follows:

$$\alpha = \text{abs}(\rho) \frac{\sigma_{\text{ref}}}{\sigma_{\text{em}}}$$

$$\beta = (1 - \rho^2)^{1/2} \frac{\sigma_{\text{ref}}}{\sigma_e}$$

Where ρ is the correlation between the ensemble-mean of the retrospective predictions and the reference dataset; σ_{ref} is the standard deviation of the reference; σ_{em} is the standard deviation of the ensemble-mean (the time series of x_i) and σ_e is the standard deviation of the hindcast ensemble.

The coefficients α and β are found using two constraints: the first is that the standard deviation of the inflated prediction is the same as that for the reference, and the second is that the predictable signal after the inflation is made equal to the correlation of the ensemble-mean with the reference dataset.

4.3.2. VERIFICATION

If a forecast is a prediction of the future state of the atmosphere, then verification is the process of assessing the quality of the forecast. The forecast is compared (i.e. verified) using a corresponding observation of what actually occurred. The verification could be qualitative ("a simple visual comparison") or quantitative. Verification should provide information about the nature of the forecast errors, and thus help to direct model development and improve the quality of the forecasts.

The quality of the monthly and 3-month average seasonal predictions of maximum and minimum temperature and precipitation from SEAS4 and SEAS5 have been assessed against the JRA-55 reanalysis (1981/1993-2015). This forecast quality assessment has been achieved through the computation of four verification metrics: the Ensemble-mean Correlation (ENSCOR, deterministic), the Fair Ranked Probability Skill Score (FRPSS, probabilistic), the Fair Continuous Ranked Probability Skill Score (FCRPSS, probabilistic) and reliability diagrams (probabilistic). This forecast quality assessment has been performed before and after the application of the bias adjustments techniques to evaluate their effect on the quality of the predictions.

4.3.2.1. ENSEMBLE-MEAN CORRELATION (ENSCOR)

The Pearson correlation coefficient (Wilks, 2011) between the ensemble-mean hindcast and the reference data set has been used as a measure of the linear correspondence between the retrospective predictions and the reference. This coefficient, represented here as r_{xy} , can be defined as:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2 (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

where x_i and y_i are, respectively, the observed and the ensemble-mean predicted values in each season, over the years $i=1,2,\dots,n$. The \bar{x} and \bar{y} are the average of the ensemble-mean predictions and the observations over the n years.

The EnsCor correlation ranges between -1 and 1. If $r_{xy} = 1$ there is a perfect association between the ensemble-mean of the hindcast and the observations. If $r_{xy} = 0$ there is no association between the ensemble-mean of the hindcast and the reference dataset. This latter case would show that the ensemble-mean of the predictions does not provide any added value relative to the retrospective climatology. Values of EnsCor less than zero ($r_{xy} < 0$) indicate that the observed climatology should be used instead of the predictions. A positive EnsCor value is the minimum requirement for seasonal predictions to have some potentially useful information, because it depends not only on the potential predictability but also on the precise distribution of the data (Jolliffe and Stephenson, 2012).

4.3.2.2. RANKED PROBABILITY SKILL SCORE (RPSS)

The ranked probability skill score (RPSS) is a comprehensive measure to evaluate the predictive skill of categorical events from probabilistic seasonal forecasts (Wilks 2011). It is derived from the ranked probability score (RPS). The RPS is the sum of the squared distance between the cumulative probabilities of the n prediction - reference pairs (for the entire interannual series) for k equally probable forecast categories (e.g. terciles):

$$RPS = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^K \left[\left(\sum_{j=1}^k y_{i,j} \right) - \left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_{i,j} \right) \right]^2$$

where y_{ij} and x_{ij} are, respectively, the predicted and observed probabilities assigned by the i th forecast ($i = 1, \dots, n$) to the k th category ($k = 1, \dots, K$). The $x_{ij} = 1$ indicates that the observation is in category k , and $x_{ij} = 0$ otherwise.

The RPS is often converted to a skill score (ranked probability skill score, RPSS) because it allows the prediction's added value relative to the climatology to be assessed. The RPSS is calculated as shown below:

$$RPSS = 1 - \frac{RPS}{RPS_{clim}}$$

The RPSS ranges from $-\infty$ to 1. RPSS values below zero are defined as unskillful, those equal to zero indicate that the forecast provides similar information to the climatology, and RPSS greater than zero shows that the predictions are better than the climatology. RPSS equal to 1 corresponds to a 'perfect' forecast.

In this deliverable the RPSS has been computed for the verification of terciles (three equiprobable categories associated with the two terciles of the climatological distribution of the reference). The probabilities have been computed as the fraction of ensemble members in the corresponding category.

4.3.2.3. CONTINUOUS RANKED PROBABILITY SKILL SCORE (CRPSS)

The continuous ranked probability skill score (CRPSS) is a commonly used skill score that allows the predictive skill of the full probability distribution to be assessed (Jolliffe and Stephenson, 2012). It is based on the continuous ranked probability score (CRPS), a score that reduces to the mean absolute error if a deterministic forecast is used (Wilks, 2011). CRPS can be expressed as:

$$CRPS = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [F(y) - F_0(y)]^2 dy$$

where $F(y)$ is the cumulative density function of the predictions and $F_0(y)$ is the cumulative step function that jumps from 0 to 1 at the point where the forecast variable (y) equals the observation (x):

$$F_0 = \begin{cases} 0, & y < x \\ 1, & y \geq x \end{cases}$$

The CRPS measures the difference between the predicted and observed cumulative distributions and it can be converted into a skill score (CRPSS), measuring the performance of a forecast relative to the climatology:

$$CRPSS = 1 - \frac{CRPS}{CRPS_{clim}}$$

The CRPSS ranges between $-\infty$ to 1. CRPSS values below zero are defined as unskillful, those equal to zero indicate that the forecast is similar to the climatology forecast. CRPSS greater than zero shows that the predictions are better than the climatology and have some skill. A CRPSS equal to 1 would indicate a 'perfect' forecast.

4.3.2.4. FAIR SCORES (FRPSS AND FCRPSS)

Fair scores for ensemble predictions have been recently introduced (Fricker et al. 2013; Ferro, 2014). A skill score is fair when it favours predictions with ensemble members that perform as if they have been sampled from the same distribution as the reference dataset. The fair version of the ranked probability skill score (FRPSS) and continuous ranked probability skill score CRPSS (FCRPSS) has been used in order to give an estimate of what the skill would be for an infinite ensemble size (a measure of potential skill).

4.3.2.5. RELIABILITY DIAGRAMS

Reliability diagrams are a common diagnostic of probabilistic predictions that assess both reliability and skill. They consist of a plot of the observed relative frequency against the predicted probability of a dichotomous event, providing a quick visual assessment of the impact of tuning probabilistic forecast systems. A perfectly reliable system should draw a line as closely as possible to the leading diagonal, within a certain measure of uncertainty.

Reliability diagrams have been used to evaluate the three forecast events defined by terciles. To draw a reliability diagram, discretization and grouping into probability bins of the probability predictions is required. The reliability diagram also includes information about the frequency of the forecast probabilities in each event, which is known as a sharpness diagram. Sharpness is a property of the predictions that gives an indication of the variation in forecast probabilities issued by the prediction system, independently of the observations.

The information provided by the reliability diagram should be interpreted with care because even a perfectly reliable forecast system is not expected to have an exactly diagonal reliability diagram owing to the limited number of samples typical of seasonal forecast systems (Jolliffe and Stephenson, 2012). To deal with this problem consistency bars (Bröcker and Smith, 2007) have been included in these diagrams. They indicate how likely the observed relative frequencies are, under the assumption that predicted probabilities are accurate.

4.4. FORECAST QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF TEMPERATURE AND

PRECIPITATION In this section the forecast quality of surface air temperature and precipitation from seasonal predictions by SEAS5, GloSea5 and MF6 is assessed using JRA-55 as the reference dataset. The two meteorological variables were averaged over July-August-September (JAS). The forecast were initialised on the 1st of June for three domains: global, European and Colombia. The analysis is focused on these regions, variables and season as an example. However, it is important to remark the study has also been conducted on a global scale and the results have been obtained for both monthly and 3-month averages with seasonal predictions initialised on 1st day of each month of the year. These results have been obtained before and after the application of the calibration adjustment (the amount of generated figures is of the order of 20,000).

4.4.1. IMPACT OF CALIBRATION ON RELIABILITY

The use of calibration to reduce model biases improves the statistical properties of the essential climate variables provided by the seasonal forecasting models. The impact of the calibration on the quality of the predictions has been tested with several different scoring measures. In this section, the effect of calibration methods on the predictions from SEAS5 is illustrated by the use of reliability diagrams.

Figure 4-1 depicts the SEAS5-JRA55 reliability diagrams for Europe and the JAS season for surface air temperature (left column) and precipitation (right column). The top row contains the raw forecasts (panels a and b), and the bottom row shows the calibrated predictions (panels c and d). For this season, the calibration reduces the reliability of the precipitation forecasts (especially for the upper and low tercile categories, see panel d). As discussed in the previous section, seasonal forecasts of precipitation show limited predictability over Europe, thus the bias adjustments introduce some uncertainty that is translated into a reduction of the precipitation forecast quality. By contrast, the calibration correction does improve the reliability of the raw forecasts of air temperature, mainly for the upper and lower terciles.

That said, it is worth noting that the central category shows systematically worse reliability than the other two, both for temperature and precipitation. We might consider that these extreme terciles are often a consequence of the additive / persistent nature of the anomalies in the boundary systems (they provide the seasonal predictability to the atmosphere). Thus, the model might find it easier to predict these extremes than the central category, for even when there is no dominant anomaly in the boundary systems, the anomalies in temperature and/ or precipitation might as well appear. This result has been previously documented (Van den Dool and Tott, 1991).

Figure 4-1: SEAS5-JRA55 reliability diagrams for Europe and the JAS season (forecasts start on the 1st of June) for air temperature (left column) and precipitation (right column) for the period 1994-2015. (a-b) Raw forecasts, (c-d) calibrated forecasts. Red refers to the above-normal category, yellow to the normal and blue to the below-normal.

4.4.2. DETERMINISTIC AND PROBABILISTIC SKILL SCORES OF CALIBRATED PREDICTIONS

This evaluation aims to assess different aspects of the forecasts, for which more than one metric is recommended. Although we have used four different skill scores (ENSCOR, FRPSS, CFRPSS and reliability diagrams), the sheer amount of information available (~20000 figures) made us select for the analysis only one season, JAS, one lead, 1st June start date, and two different metrics: ENSCOR (deterministic) and FRPSS (probabilistic). The analysis is performed for 2m temperature and precipitation and for three different regions: global, Europe and Colombia, considering three models: SEAS5, MF6 and GloSea5.

4.4.2.1. GLOBAL

In the global domain, the skill for temperature is always higher than that for precipitation (compare Figure 4-2 and Figure 4-3), as evidenced by the larger areas with ENSCOR values above 0.75 in Figure 4-2 (shown in red). This is evident in all months, lead-times, models and skill scores, as shown in Figures 4-2, 4-3, 4-4 and 4-5, because temperature is usually easier to model than precipitation. In addition, the intertropical regions show better performance, especially in the Pacific Ocean. This is an expected result since an important amount of model's predictability comes from the coupling with sea surface temperature (SST), and El Niño is one of the main drivers at these time scales (Doblas-Reyes, 2013). Another feature linked to the previous statement is that the skill is greater over the oceans than inland. This is consequence of the 'memory' both boundary elements have, the ocean the one with a greater impact on the general circulation.

There are areas of consistent positive skill scores for temperature (Figures 4-2 and 4-4) in wide regions of North America, Central America and northern South America. In Eurasia, there are interesting regions in the Middle East, south-eastern Asia and scattered regions in the extra-tropics. The differences among the models are rather small and limited to some

areas such as northern Europe, Australia, Africa and north-western North America. However, these differences also suggest that building a multi-model ensemble could be an interesting strategy to maximize the predictability of these forecasts. Finally, turning to precipitation, the skill is very patchy in all three models, although there are areas of Indonesia, Central America, South-America and Australia that hold some skill (Figures 4-3 and 4-5).

Figure 4-2: Global ensemble mean correlation, ENSCOR, for JAS (July-August-September; 1st June start date) JRA55 calibrated 2m temperature forecasts for three systems: SEAS5 (left above), MF6 (right above) and GloSea5 (below). Hatching refers to correlations statistically significant at 95% confidence level. The period of the analysis is 1994-2015.

Figure 4-3: Global ensemble mean correlation, ENSCOR, for JAS (July-August-September; 1st June start date) JRA55 calibrated precipitation forecasts for three systems: SEAS5 (left above), MF6 (right above) and GloSea5 (below). Hatching refers to correlations statistically significant at 95% confidence level. The period of the analysis is 1994-2015.

Figure 4-4: Global fair ranked probability skill score, FRPSS, for JAS (July-August-September; 1st June start date) JRA55 calibrated 2m temperature forecasts for three systems: SEAS5 (left above), MF6 (right above) and GloSea5 (below). The period of the analysis is 1994-2015.

Figure 4-5: Global fair ranked probability skill score, FRPSS, for JAS (July-August-September; 1st June start date) JRA55 calibrated precipitation forecasts for three systems: SEAS5 (left above), MF6 (right above) and GloSea5 (below). The period of the analysis is 1994-2015.

4.4.2.2. EUROPE

Temperature correlations show an area of decreased skill in northern Europe (white areas in Figure 4-6). This area can be seen in all three models, though with different sizes, which suggests there is a physical process that it is not well represented by the physics within the models. The areas of higher skill lie in the south-eastern part of the domain and some areas in the Atlantic and Iberian Peninsula. The FRPSS is higher than zero for most of the regions in Europe, which means that the use of seasonal predictions provides an added value with respect to climatology (Figure 4-7). More specifically, FRPSS lies between 0 and 0.25 over most of the continental Europe whereas over the Atlantic and the south-eastern part of Europe, the values increase up to 0.25-0.50.

Figure 4-6: European ensemble mean correlation, ENSCOR, for JAS (July-August-September; 1st June start date) JRA55 calibrated 2m temperature forecasts for three systems: SEAS5 (left above), MF6 (right above) and GloSea5 (below). Hatching refers to correlations statistically significant at 95% confidence level. The period of the analysis is 1994-2015.

In contrast, the precipitation performance is rather poor. The areas of skill (shown by the ENSCOR metric) are patchy and differ between the models (Figure 4-8), although SEAS5 and GloSea5 have some skill over the south-eastern Mediterranean. The skill over the Med-GOLD study regions (northern Portugal, southern Spain and Italy) is very low. The areas with FRPSS scores above zero are very patchy, and values above zero are mostly smaller than 0.25 (Figure 4-9).

Figure 4-7: European fair ranked probability skill score, FRPSS, for JAS (July-August-September; 1st June start date) JRA55 calibrated 2m temperature forecasts for three systems: SEAS5 (left above), MF6 (right above) and GloSea5 (below). The period of the analysis is 1994-2015.

Figure 4-8: European ensemble mean correlation, ENSCOR, for JAS (July-August-September; 1st June start date) JRA55 calibrated precipitation forecasts for three systems: SEAS5 (left above), MF6 (right above) and GloSea5 (below). Hatching refers to correlations statistically significant at 95% confidence level. The period of the analysis is 1994-2015.

Figure 4-9: European fair ranked probability skill score, FRPSS, for JAS (July-August-September; 1st June start date) JRA55 calibrated precipitation forecasts for three systems: SEAS5 (left above), MF6 (right above) and GloSea5 (below). The period of the analysis is 1994-2015.

4.4.2.3. COLOMBIA

Colombia, in particular coffee crops, are another area of interest for MED-GOLD, as was set out in Task 6.2. PBDMs have already been developed for coffee, and provide some information on the main climate-related problems including key pests. This information would serve as a starting point for development of a climate service for coffee. An assessment of seasonal forecast skill over Colombia is therefore important, as data from these forecast models could be used to drive PBDMs as part of delivery of a climate service.

In the Colombian domain, the seasonal forecasts skill is quite high for both temperature and precipitation (Figures 4-10 to 4-13). This is probably due to the influence of the tropical Pacific and Atlantic oceans that extend their predictability to the inland circulations. In the case of temperature, the ensemble correlation is always between 0.25 and 1 in all the areas, with extensive regions above 0.5 and 0.75 (Figure 4-10). Regarding the FRPSS, it is above zero almost everywhere, with many areas above 0.25 (Figure 4-11), especially the sea-shores.

For precipitation, the skill is lower, but still surpasses the climatology in many areas, both for ENSCOR (Figure 4-12) and for FRPSS (Figure 4-13). This behaviour can be observed in all of the models and the existence of differences pave the way to improve the predictions by designing a multi-model approach.

4.5. SUMMARY

Seasonal forecasts from three different models have been evaluated globally, and over Europe and Colombia. The forecast skill for temperature is quite high over the MED-GOLD study regions. The skill for precipitation is poor over Europe but notably much better for Colombia. These differences in skill are related to the large-scale processes which control atmospheric circulation. Climate over Colombia is strongly controlled by the El Niño-La Niña cycle, which is predicted well by the models. The summer climate over northwest Europe is partly controlled by the Atlantic Multi-decadal Oscillation (AMO), a large-scale pattern of variability in sea surface temperatures in the north Atlantic, and the summertime north Atlantic oscillation. However, there are fewer significant correlations between large-scale climate and precipitation across Europe during summer, possibly suggesting that warm-season precipitation is predominantly generated by local or regional scale convective systems. These convective systems are not simulated well by the seasonal forecast models.

Figure 4-10: Colombian ensemble mean correlation, ENSCOR, for JAS (July-August-September; 1st June start date) JRA55 calibrated 2m temperature forecasts for three systems: SEAS5 (left above), MF6 (right above) and GloSea5 (below). Hatching refers to correlations statistically significant at 95% confidence level. The period of the analysis is 1994-2015.

Figure 4-11: Colombian fair ranked probability skill score, FRPSS, for JAS (July-August-September; 1st June start date) JRA55 calibrated 2m temperature forecasts for three systems: SEAS5 (left above), MF6 (right above) and GloSea5 (below). The period of the analysis is 1994-2015.

Figure 4-12: Colombian ensemble mean correlation, ENSCOR, for JAS (July-August-September; 1st June start date) JRA55 calibrated precipitation forecasts for three systems: SEAS5 (left above), MF6 (right above) and GloSea5 (below). Hatching refers to correlations statistically significant at 95% confidence level. The period of the analysis is 1994-2015.

Figure 4-13: Colombian fair ranked probability skill score, FRPSS, for JAS (July-August-September; 1st June start date) JRA55 calibrated precipitation forecasts for three systems: SEAS5 (left above), MF6 (right above) and GloSea5 (below). The period of the analysis is 1994-2015.

5. EVALUATION OF EURO-CORDEX SIMULATIONS

Assessing the impacts of expected twenty-first century climate change and developing response strategies requires local- to regional-scale information on the nature of these changes. An integral part of these regional model projections is the evaluation and quantification of model performance by comparison against observation-based reference data. For this purpose, the standard procedure is to carry out evaluation experiments for the recent decades (e.g., Kotlarski et al. (2014) and references therein).

At the time of writing, EURO-CORDEX simulations are the highest resolution climate data available for Europe. The performance of an ensemble of five state-of-the-art RCM simulations (Table 5-1) produced under the EURO-CORDEX initiative (www.euro-cordex.net) is assessed. These five simulations were chosen to sample several different RCM and GCMs. Availability of simulations under two emissions scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) and longer-term control simulations was also a factor in the choice of models. The meteorological information from these models will be used to study key climatic variables within each of the work packages developing tools for users (WPs 2, 3 and 4), and also to drive crop models. Key climatic indicators for each of the three crops could also be calculated and used to understand possible impacts of climate change on areas suitable for the crops as well as yields, quality and other aspects.

The RCM simulations studied here were executed at a resolution of 0.11° (about 12 km), and are compared with the E-OBS v17 dataset (resolution 0.22°; approximately 25 km) for the period 1971-2000. The E-OBS data have a lower resolution than the RCMs, therefore the RCM simulations were aggregated onto the 0.22° grid used by E-OBS. More specifically, the aggregation was achieved by calculating an area-weighted average of all grid cells of the RCM grid that overlapped with each of the E-OBS grid boxes (Kotlarski et al. 2014).

Table 5-1: List of EURO-CORDEX simulations analysed

Institute	RCM	GCM
SMHI	RCA4	HadGEM2-ES CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5
IPSL-INERIS	WRF331F	IPSL-IPSL-CM5A-MR
KNMI	RACMO22E	ICHEC-EC-EARTH
MPI-CSC	REMO2009	MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR

A selected number of indices from the 27 ETCCDI (Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices) core climate change indices for essential climate variables (ECVs) of temperature and precipitation (Table 6.2) were used in the assessment. The selection of these indices was based on meteorological variables identified by participants in the workshops held during May and June 2018 ([RD.2], [RD.3] and [RD.4]), and the meteorological variables available from E-OBS (section 3.1).

In section 5.1 the climate model simulations are evaluated for the entire Mediterranean region. A more detailed analysis for the Douro Valley in Portugal and Andalusia region in Spain is presented in section 5.2. Projections of future climate for these regions is analysed in section 5.3.

Table 5-2: List of climatic indices used to assess the RCM simulations

Index	Description	Definition
Tg	Mean of daily mean temperature	Average temperature in a given period
Tx	Mean of daily maximum temperature	Average temperature in a given period
Tn	Mean of daily minimum temperature	Average temperature in a given period
SU	Summer days	Number of days with Tx > 25°C
TR	Tropical nights	Number of days with Tn > 20°C
TOTPREC (or RR)	Total precipitation	Total precipitation in a given period
CDD	Consecutive dry days	Largest number of consecutive days where precipitation < 1 mm
RR1	Number of wet days	Total number of days when precipitation > 1 mm
RR10	Heavy precipitation days	Total number of days when precipitation > 10 mm

5.1. ASSESSMENT OVER THE MEDITERRANEAN

An overview of the spatial distribution of the 30-year mean winter and summer ensemble model biases is shown for daily mean temperature (Figure 5-1) and daily total precipitation (Figure 5-2). For temperature, the evaluation indicates important biases in individual models. In wintertime, temperatures are underestimated over large parts of the Mediterranean. The largest negative biases (cooler than -3°C) are found in the western part of the domain (ICHEC-EC-EARTH-RACMO22), and along the Alpine ridge (all models). Only one model (MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR-REMO2009) shows a warm bias of more than $+2^{\circ}\text{C}$, mostly over Balkans. Cold biases are also evident for the summer months, but are generally smaller. Higher biases than winter are only evident for the CNRM-CM5-RRAC4 and IPSL-WRF331 RCMs.

Concerning seasonal mean precipitation, the evaluation indicates a wet wintertime bias in most models over large parts of the Mediterranean (Fig. 6.2). Biases of more than 50% are present over much of the region. In summer, most of the models overestimate precipitation totals over the Iberian Peninsula, Italy and Greece. It should be noted that in most of the models, the precipitation bias exhibits a pronounced spatial variability, which is higher than the temperature variability. The ICHEC-EC-EARTH-RACMO22 model has the lowest bias in both seasons.

Based on the above initial analysis we opt to calibrate the models output based on the E-OBS for the areas of the Douro Valley and Andalusia since the model data will be used to drive impact models simulations as well as to calculate risk indexes in the WP2 and WP3 respectively. To this aim we employ the empirical quantile mapping (EQM) for calibration (Annex B). For WP4 [RD.4], EOBS was not found to be a suitable dataset for bias correction/downscaling and instead point observations were used. Hence, in the following sections, a detailed comparison between E-OBS and EURO-CORDEX over Italy has not been made.

Figure 5-1: Mean seasonal temperature biases for all RCM simulations over the period 1971–2000. Upper two rows: winter (DJF), lower two rows: summer (JJA). The upper-left panel of each section shows the horizontal pattern of mean seasonal temperature from the E-OBS reference dataset. Negative and positive values in the other panels indicate that the modelled data are cooler or warmer respectively than E-OBS. All panels show temperatures in $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure 5-2: Mean relative seasonal total precipitation biases (%) for all RCM simulations over the period 1971–2000. Upper two rows: winter (DJF), lower two rows: summer (JJA). The upper-left panel of each section shows the horizontal pattern of mean seasonal precipitation from E-OBS (units of mm per season). In the remaining panels, blue and red colours show areas where precipitation amounts in the modelled data are higher and lower than E-OBS respectively.

5.2. RESULTS FOR THE DOURO VALLEY AND ANDALUSIA

Two main approaches have been used to evaluate the RCMs over the Douro valley and Andalusia. The simulated and observed climatologies (spatial patterns) are compared for the temperature and precipitation indices shown in Table 6.2. The comparisons between the simulated and observed climatologies are summarized using Taylor diagrams (Taylor, 2001). These diagrams synthesize three spatial measures – standard deviation (S), centred root-mean-square difference (R), and correlation (C) – into a single two dimensional figure. Similar to Turco et al. (2017), two variations from the standard Taylor diagram have been applied in this report:

- The measures S and R are normalized, dividing them by the standard deviation of the observations. In this way it is possible to compare the different indices.
- Information about spatial average of the bias (M) has been introduced (using colours) for each point in the Taylor diagram. In particular, we use the differences between the simulated and observed mean, normalized by the observed mean.

In order to assess the correspondence of the simulated and observed annual cycles, we analyse the performance of the method in both the Douro Valley and Andalusia at a monthly scale. To this aim, we calculated several monthly indices spatially averaged for the two areas.

5.2.1. MEAN CLIMATE

As an illustrative example, maps showing annually averaged values over the period 1971-2000 of the three indices Tx, Tn and RR from E-OBS, the raw (i.e. uncalibrated) model data, and the calibrated model data (using the EQM method)

are shown in Figure 5-3 for the Douro valley and Figure 5-4 for Andalusia. The models shown are those with the lowest biases. From these figures it is evident that each model performs better for a specific index and no model has a better skill across all indices. In addition, it is shown that the EQM calibrated values are almost identical to the observed ones, indicating that the method succeeds in correcting the modelled values.

Figure 5-3: Spatial distribution of three of the ECVs over the Douro valley: top row, Tx; middle row, Tn; bottom row, RR. The indices were calculated from E-OBS (left column), raw RCM (middle column) and calibrated RCM data using EQM (right column). All data are average values over the period 1971–2000. The spatial validation scores for the RCM and EQM simulated values are given below the corresponding panels: M - mean error (in % with respect to the observed mean); S - relative standard deviation; R - centred root-mean-square; and C - correlation. Note that the scales for Tx and Tn are not the same.

Figure 5-4: As Figure 5-3 but for Andalusia. Note that the scales for Tx and Tn are different.

The Taylor diagrams shown in Figure 5-5 summarize the results for all the models and indices in the control period (1971–2000) for both the Douro Valley and Andalusia. These figures show that, overall, the EQM calibration method improves the RCM results for all the indices, with standard deviations and spatial correlations similar to the observed ones. In terms of errors, the EQM method also reduces the RCM bias (M) and the centred root-mean-square error (R). In particular, the EQM calibration clearly reduces the underestimation of the temperature indices (both maximum and minimum temperature indices) by the RCMs. The models overestimate the TR index (Number of Tropical Nights) compared with E-OBS in both the Douro valley and Andalusia.

For precipitation, calibration with EQM clearly reduces the overestimation of the RCMs (compare the lowest three panels of Figure 5-3 and Figure 5-4), with the exception of CDD (Figure 5-5), where the models still underestimate the number relative to E-OBS. Overall, the EQM method is able to reduce the biases as indicated by the metrics for different indices for all RCMs, even for the worst performing models (e.g., TR in Andalusia).

Figure 5-5: Taylor diagrams for the GCM-RCM pairs for the different indices (Table 6.2) over the Douro valley and Andalucia. The circles and the squares on each panel indicate the raw and calibrated model output respectively. Note that in some cases the calibrated data from individual GCM-RCM pairs are co-located. In all cases, the calibrated data are much closer to the point marked 'E-OBS' than the raw data (circles). Results from the IPSL-WRF331 model are missing from the two panels for the R10 metric in Andalusia owing to the slightly negative spatial correlation coefficients of the model output (which is calibrated by the EQM with a value similar to the rest of the calibrated models). Note that the horizontal and vertical axes of each panel have the same scale.

5.2.2. SEASONAL CYCLES

In Figure 5-6, the seasonal cycles of four temperature-based indices (Tx, Tn, SU and TR) and four precipitation-based indices (TOTPR, CDD, RR1 and R10) from E-OBS are compared with those calculated from the raw and calibrated RCM data (see Table 5-2 for a description of the indices). It is evident that RCMs (using both the raw and calibrated data) are able to reproduce the observed seasonal cycles of the indices for the Douro Valley and Andalusia (Figure 5-6). The spread between the models (as shown by the red shaded areas) is reduced following calibration (blue shaded areas). The RCM performance for precipitation (considering the raw data) is poorer over Andalusia than the Douro valley. A summer maximum is seen in the TOTPREC, RR1 and R10 indices in Andalusia that is not present in E-OBS. This erroneous peak is removed following calibration (blue areas).

Figure 5-6: Seasonal cycle of the spatially averaged indices (Table 6.2) for the Douro Valley and Andalusia. The black line represents the E-OBS climatology. The light red-shaded band corresponds to the range of the values from the raw RCM data, while the light blue one indicates the calibrated values.

5.3. FUTURE PROJECTIONS

The regional climate change signals for two different future periods (2031-2060 and 2071-2100) from the baseline (1971-2000) are analysed for the climatic indices listed in Table 5-2 for both the Douro Valley and Andalusia. Results are shown under two different emissions scenarios, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. In all figures, projected changes using both the raw and calibrated RCM data (ENS-RAW and ENS-EQM respectively) are shown. In general, there is a good agreement between the RCM regional climate change signal and the one obtained by EQM. The highest agreement is found for the mean seasonal changes for both periods and under both future emission scenarios and for all examined variables. Lower agreement, mostly spatial, is found for the threshold based indices calculated for the daily maximum and minimum temperatures and the daily total precipitation. In this section, figures illustrating results for the Douro valley are shown. Corresponding figures for Andalusia may be found in Annex C.

Seasonal maximum temperatures (T_x) are projected to increase in both the Douro Valley (Figure 5-7 and Figure 5-8) and Andalusia (Figure C-3 and Figure C-4) under both emission scenarios and the two future periods. For the Douro Valley the highest increases in mean daily maximum temperatures are found in the summer (JJA) period, reaching about 4.6°C by the 2080s (Figure 5-8).

The numbers of summer days (SU) are also projected to increase, and the numbers are larger under the RCP8.5 scenario than the RCP4.5 scenario in both future time periods. For the near-term future period (2031-2060), the average number of summer days under the RCP8.5 scenario is 25-26 days, compared with about 22 under the RCP4.5 scenario. By the end of the twenty-first century, the differences between the two scenarios are much greater (52 days under RCP8.5, and 30 days under RCP4.5), reflecting the higher emissions of greenhouse gases under the RCP8.5 scenario (Annex D, section D.4).

For Andalusia, the highest mean increases in T_x are also found for the summer period, reaching about 4.9°C (Figure C-3). Increases are also projected in the numbers of summer days (SU), varying from about 22 extra days per year under the RCP4.5 scenario (2031-2060, Figure C-3) and 58 days under the RCP8.5 scenario for 2071-2100 (Figure C-4).

Similar to T_x , increases are also projected in minimum temperatures (T_n), for all seasons, scenarios and future time periods. The largest increases in mean daily minimum temperatures were found for summer (JJA), reaching about 3.9°C for the Douro Valley (Figure 5-10) and 4.1°C in Andalusia (Figure C-6), for 2071-2100 under the RCP8.5 scenario. The numbers of tropical nights are projected to increase, from 5 to 33 (RCP4.5, 2031-2060) to 23 to 65 extra days per year (RCP8.5, 2071-2100) respectively for the Douro Valley and Andalusia (Figure 5-9 and Figure C-6 respectively).

For the precipitation indices, non-significant changes or small increases were projected for 2031-2060 under the RCP4.5 scenario for the Douro Valley in winter under RCP4.5 and autumn under RCP8.5 (Figure 5-11). For the rest of the simulations, decreases in precipitation are projected for the mean seasonal precipitation with the highest relative decreases found in spring (MAM). As a result the average annual numbers of wet days decreases for all experiments, by 6 to 17 fewer days per year under RCP4.5 (2031-2060; Figure 5-11) and RCP8.5 (2071-2100; Figure 5-12) respectively. Larger decreases in rainfall are projected for Andalusia. The greatest decreases were calculated for the spring (MAM) and summer (JJA) under RCP8.5 (2071-2100, Figure C-8).

Figure 5-7: Changes in seasonal mean Tx between 2031-2060 and 1971-2000 from the RCM ensemble mean over the Douro valley. Results calculated from calibrated simulations (ENS-EQM) and the raw model data (ENS-RAW) are shown, under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. The bottom row shows annual changes in SU index (the numbers of summer days) under each scenario, using calibrated and raw data.

Figure 5-8: Changes in seasonal mean Tx between 2071-2100 and 1971-2000 from the RCM ensemble mean over the Douro valley. Results calculated from calibrated simulations (ENS-EQM) and the raw model data (ENS-RAW) are shown, under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. The bottom row shows annual changes in SU index (the numbers of summer days) under each scenario, using calibrated and raw data.

Figure 5-9: Changes in seasonal mean Tn over the Douro valley between 2031-2060 and 1971-2000 from the RCM ensemble mean. Results were calculated from calibrated simulations (ENS-EQM) and the raw model data (ENS-RAW), under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. The bottom row shows mean annual changes in the numbers of tropical nights (TR).

Figure 5-10: Changes in seasonal mean Tn over the Douro valley between 2071-2100 and 1971-2000 from the RCM ensemble mean. Results were calculated from calibrated simulations (ENS-EQM) and the raw model data (ENS-RAW), under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. The bottom row shows mean annual changes in the numbers of tropical nights (TR).

Figure 5-11: Changes in seasonal mean precipitation (RR) over the Douro Valley between 2031-2060 and 1971-2000 for the five member RCM ensemble. Results from the calibrated (ENS-EQM) and raw model output (ENS-RAW) are shown under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. The bottom row illustrates changes in the mean annual numbers of wet days (RR1).

Figure 5-12: Changes in seasonal mean precipitation (RR) over the Douro Valley between 2071-2100 and 1971-2000 for the five member RCM ensemble. Results from the calibrated (ENS-EQM) and raw model output (ENS-RAW) are shown under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. The bottom row illustrates changes in the mean annual numbers of wet days (RR1).

6. EVALUATION OF CAM-CORDEX SIMULATIONS OVER COLOMBIA

Colombia, in particular coffee crops, are another area of interest for MED-GOLD (see section 4.4.2.3). An assessment of climate change projections over Colombia is important, as data from climate models could be used to calculate coffee crop-relevant indices, and drive PBDMs as part of a climate service.

In this section, climate simulations over Colombia and surrounding countries in the Central American CORDEX simulations (CAM-CORDEX) are assessed (further details regarding CAM-CORDEX may be found in Annex A, section A.2). A brief summary of previously published assessments of climate change in Colombia is given first. Next, key ECVs from the CAM-CORDEX climate simulations and AgMERRA are compared. A full assessment of all of the CAM-CORDEX simulations is beyond the scope of this report, but comparisons of simple metrics is presented here for selected models. The creation of calibrated climate projections for Colombia for driving crop models can be found in section 8.

6.1. PREVIOUS CLIMATE CHANGE ASSESSMENTS FOR COLOMBIA

A small number of studies have evaluated climate model simulations over Colombia and examined projected changes in climate. Unfortunately, none of these studies used the CAM-CORDEX simulations. In an earlier study, a RCM with a resolution of 20 km was integrated over Colombia for 10- and 20-year periods (World Bank, 2007). The RCM was driven using observed and simulated sea surface temperatures (SSTs). The results shown focused on January. For this month, both sets of simulations had too much rain over the higher altitude regions of Colombia.

The climate of the future period, 2080-2099, was simulated under the SRES A1B scenario (emissions are closest to the RCP6.0 scenario, and so are lower than those under the RCP8.5 scenario). In one future simulation, projected changes in SSTs were added to observed SSTs to drive the RCM, whereas in the other future simulation the RCM was driven by modelled SSTs (World Bank, 2007). The first simulation projected small decreases in rainfall over the higher altitude regions, whereas the second projected increases in precipitation. In contrast, both sets of simulations projected fairly uniform increases in temperature over Colombia for January, between 1.5 and 3 °C.

Cabos et al. (2019) evaluated a small number of regional model simulations that used the CAM-CORDEX domain, but focused on Central America. No results were reported for Colombia. Solman et al. (2013) evaluated climate simulations from seven RCMs integrated using the South American CORDEX domain. They focused on several different areas, none of which included Colombia. An evaluation of RCM performance over Colombia is therefore required.

Ramirez-Villegas et al. (2013) evaluated a large number of GCM simulations from CMIP3 and CMIP5 over many countries, including Colombia. They showed that modelled errors in seasonal average temperature and precipitation were large, in the range 1-18°C and over 100% for precipitation. The ability of the models to reproduce the variability of temperature and precipitation over Colombia was also low. These results are important, as any errors in the GCM climate will also be present in the CAM-CORDEX RCM simulations. The RCMs produce a higher-resolution (i.e. downscaled) version of the same climate as simulated by the GCM, although there will be some local-scale differences, as the RCMs can resolve smaller-scale climatic and orographic features.

6.2. EVALUATION OF CAM-CORDEX FOR COLOMBIA

No publications assessing simulations of climate by the CAM-CORDEX regional climate models over Colombia are known. The few publications using CAM-CORDEX data have focused on Mexico and Central America. In this section, simulations of maximum and minimum temperatures and precipitation from the CAM-CORDEX ensemble of regional climate models are compared with the AgMERRA data, with a focus on Colombia. All of the CAM-CORDEX simulations assessed in this section are taken from two groups (Annex A, section A.2):

Evaluation, where the RCMs were forced by the ERA-Interim reanalysis;

Historical, where the RCMs were forced by different GCMs.

A comparison of the simulations of a particular meteorological variable between these two groups shows the likely sources of biases. If the simulations are dissimilar, the differences lie with the driving data (i.e. differences in the climate in ERA-Interim and the GCMs). If they are similar, then the biases will partly originate within the RCM.

Data for the period 1980 – 2005 from both groups were used in the assessments. Under CMIP5, the historical period ended in 2005, and the projection (or scenario) period began in 2006. Data are available from AgMERRA for 1980 – 2010; hence, the common period of these datasets is 1980 – 2005. Before use, all of the RCM data were bi-linearly interpolated to the regular 0.25° grid used by AgMERRA. This assessment focuses on the key variables required for agricultural modelling that are present in AgMERRA: maximum and minimum temperatures, precipitation, humidity, surface wind speeds and surface radiation. Example results are shown using the RegCM4 RCM driven by the CCCma GCM.

6.2.1. MAXIMUM TEMPERATURES

Daily maximum temperatures were calculated for the period 1981-2005 from AgMERRA, and the evaluation and historical simulations of the regional climate models. Example results for January and July are shown in Figure 6-1. The simulations have notable warm biases in maximum temperatures, of 8°C or more in some regions. The bias is present in both the evaluation and historical simulations, and has a similar magnitude. This result indicates that the bias partly originates with the RCM itself, although warm biases are also present in the driving GCMs (Ramirez-Villegas et al. 2013).

Figure 6-1: Monthly means of maximum temperatures in January (left-hand panel) and July (right-hand panel) from AgMERRA ('Obs'), evaluation simulations (where the RCM is driven by ERA-Interim) and historical simulations (the RCM driven by the Canadian GCM "CCCma") from the RCA4 RCM. The data shown are averages over 1980-2005.

6.2.2. MINIMUM TEMPERATURES

Monthly means of minimum temperatures are shown in Figure 6-2 for January and July. The biases are generally smaller than for maximum temperatures, although they are as high as 8°C in a small area to the south-east of Colombia. The columns of differences between the three sets of simulations (columns 2 and 4) show some interesting features. The shapes of areas above 2°C are similar in both the evaluation and historical simulations. In January, the warm bias is notably larger in the historical simulation than the evaluation, whereas in July the biases are smaller and very similar. The larger bias in January in the historical simulation most likely originates with the driving GCM.

Figure 6-2: Monthly means of minimum temperatures in January (left-hand panel) and July (right-hand panel) from AgMERRA, evaluation simulations (where the RCM is driven by ERA-Interim) and historical simulations (the RCM “SMHI-RCA4” driven by the Canadian GCM “CCCma”). The data shown are averages over 1980-2005.

6.2.3. PRECIPITATION

Monthly precipitation totals (averaged over 1980-2005) for January and July are shown in Figure 6-3. The biases are large (over 100%) in both seasons. Precipitation is too high over the higher altitude areas, and too small over the lower areas. These biases in the CAM-CORDEX simulations are mostly inherited from the driving GCMs, which have been shown to have large biases in precipitation over Colombia (Ramirez-Villegas et al. 2013). The precipitation patterns in the evaluation and historical simulations are very different to the pattern in AgMERRA, for which there are a number of possible reasons. AgMERRA was created from the MERRA global reanalysis, which will not capture the smaller-scale patterns in precipitation as simulated by the RCMs, owing to its coarser resolution. Few of the surface weather stations in Colombia were available in GHCN-D, and only a small number of them were used to correct the MERRA reanalysis to create AgMERRA ([RD.1]; Ruane et al. 2015).

Figure 6-3: Monthly totals of precipitation in January (left-hand panels) and July (right-hand panels) from AgMERRA, evaluation simulations (where the RCM is driven by ERA-Interim) and historical simulations (the RCM “SMHI-RCA4” driven by the Canadian GCM “CCCma”). The data shown are averages over 1980-2005. Note that 1 kg m⁻² day⁻¹ is the same as 1 mm day⁻¹.

It was not possible to compare surface relative humidity directly. Only daily mean relative humidity is available from the CAM-CORDEX simulations, whereas AgMERRA contains relative humidity at the time of maximum temperature (RHTmax). This latter variable was estimated from the RCM simulations using the procedure described in Annex D.

6.2.4. SUMMARY

The comparisons in Figures 6-1 to 6-3 show that significant biases exist in the CAM-CORDEX simulations. Results from one GCM-RCM combination are shown, but similar biases exist in simulations driven by other GCMs (data not shown). For this reason, the daily data files will be created using a “delta-change” calibration method (Annex B). Further details are given in section 7.3.

6.3. PROJECTIONS OF FUTURE CLIMATE OVER COLOMBIA

Some examples of projections of future climate for Colombia are shown here. The figures show the changes from the raw and calibrated climate data. Here, ‘baseline’ refers to climate data for 1980-2000, and ‘scenario’ means climate data for a future period (2021-2040). Monthly mean maximum temperatures for January are shown in Figure 6-4. The upper two panels show temperatures from AgMERRA and the model baseline. The warm bias in the modelled data is evident. The lower two panels show the raw and calibrated temperatures, the latter created using the SDM method (section 7.3). It can be seen that the calibration has removed the warm bias. Warming over this part of South America is projected for the future, by around 2°C.

Figure 6-4: Monthly mean maximum temperatures for January in AgMERRA, the modelled baseline. The two lower panels show the raw and calibrated scenario data.

Examples of differences between raw and calibrated precipitation data for July are shown in Figure 6-5. The percentage differences between the baseline model simulation and AgMERRA is shown in the top left panel. The model has a clear dry bias over much of the region, as shown by the dark red colour. The projected changes in precipitation are shown in the top right panel. Precipitation is projected to decrease over much of Colombia (red colours), although increases are projected to the south (blue colours). The effect of the calibration (using the SDM method; see section 7.3) is shown in the bottom left panel. The dry bias has been corrected (blue colours), while the smaller areas where the modelled precipitation was too high show that precipitation has been reduced. The percentage differences between the calibrated scenario and AgMERRA are shown in the bottom right panel of Figure 6-5. Rainfall is projected to decrease over much of the region, except at a few high altitude locations.

Figure 6-5: Percentage differences in monthly total precipitation for July. Top left: Model baseline minus AgMERRA. Top right: Percentage change between the scenario (i.e. future) and baseline time periods. Bottom left: Calibrated scenario minus raw scenario. Bottom right: Calibrated scenario minus AgMERRA.

7. CLIMATE DATA SERIES FOR CROP MODELS IN COLOMBIA

In this section, trends in coffee production in Colombia are summarised. Next, the major threats to the future of coffee crops worldwide are identified from published studies together with projected impacts on coffee plants. Finally, methods for the construction of daily series of climate variables required to drive crop models for Colombia are described.

7.1. COFFEE PRODUCTION IN COLOMBIA

Colombia is the world's third largest coffee exporter, after Brazil and Vietnam. Colombia contains many valleys, mountains, and volcanos that create the high altitudes and rich soil in which the coffee plant thrives (Barón, 2010). The coffee industry in Colombia mostly consists of small, family-owned farms, of which about 95% (over 500,000) are five hectares or less in size (García, 2003). In 2015, coffee exports accounted for between one and two percent of Colombia's GDP. Coffee farming provides many hundreds of thousands of jobs in rural areas, and is grown in three main regions as shown in Figure 7-1.

Figure 7-1: Map of major coffee-growing regions in Colombia. Reproduced from Quiñones-Ruiz et al. (2015).

Statistics for cultivated areas with coffee crops, production and export of coffee beans are available from the Federación Nacional de Cafeteros, or FNC (National Federation of Coffee Growers of Colombia; see section D.1). Areas of land cultivated with coffee crops are available from 2002. The areas increased steadily from about 860,000 ha in 2002 to 974,000 ha in 2013. The cultivated areas have then declined more rapidly to 877,000 ha in 2018, the same area as 2007.

One major disease which affects coffee plants is the coffee rust fungus. This fungus is a major problem in Central America, where it has resulted in greatly reduced yields in recent years and threatened the livelihoods of many farmers. Colombia has been less affected by this fungus, although an outbreak of rust in 1987-1988 reduced yields (Figure 7-3). Another outbreak started in 2010 which affected 33% of coffee plantations, but by February 2011 the rate had dropped to 17% and by November of that year to 10% (Avelino et al. 2015). This drop in rust infestation was partly achieved with the development and planting of rust resistant varieties of coffee crops. However, some experts believe that the fall in fungal infestation could be temporary, and the fungus may evolve over the next decade and become more widespread.

Figure 7-2: Land areas cultivated with coffee crops in Colombia (in kha). Data from FNC.

Figure 7-3: Annual coffee production in Colombia, in millions of 60 kg bags of green bean equivalent. Data from FNC.

Annual production of coffee in Colombia from 1956 to 2018 is shown in Figure 7-3. Coffee production was fairly constant at around 7 million bags up to 1976, after which it increased considerably, reaching its highest value of 16 million bags in 1992 and 1993. Production then fell back to the same levels as the 1980s. Production between 1987-1988 and 2008-2011 was low owing to outbreaks of the coffee rust fungus. During 2008-2011, the effects of an El Niño / La Niña caused additional problems, as rain, cloudiness, and hot spells all increased during the same period.

Production in the past few years (from 2015) has recovered to around 14 million bags per year (Figure 7-3), despite the decline in cultivated areas (Figure 7-2). A comparison of the cultivated areas and annual production (Figure 7-4) show that there is no clear relationship between the two, indicating that other factors such as weather conditions, disease outbreaks and farming practices have had the largest effects on production.

Figure 7-4: Annual coffee production and cultivated areas over the common period (2002 to 2018). Data from FNC.

7.2. IMPACTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON COFFEE CROPS

Climate change poses a major threat to coffee crops, and agriculture in general in Colombia (Martinez et al. 2018). Many varieties of coffee crops have been chosen or bred for their taste and other important attributes, such as resilience to disease, and all originated from wild plants. For example, around 150 years ago, coffee was widely grown in Asia, but outbreaks of coffee rust destroyed most of the crops. A wild species, *Robusta*, was identified that was resistant to leaf rust and now makes up around 40% of the global coffee trade (Davis et al. 2019). However, climate change is resulting in more severe pest outbreaks, rising temperatures and increased droughts, all of which threaten the existence of many wild species of coffee. If these wild species were to become extinct, the ability of growers to develop newer species of coffee would be severely limited. All of these effects are occurring against a background of rising demand for coffee.

Coffee grows within a fairly narrow climatic window, and so has limited capacity to adapt. A study of areas suitable for the wild Arabica coffee in Ethiopia and South Sudan and population numbers under future climates (Moat et al. 2019) projected clear reductions in both, by 50% or more, during the latter part of the twenty-first century. These reductions were driven by increased temperatures and longer droughts. Deforestation was also noted as a major threat to the survival of wild coffee. A related study by Davis et al. (2019) found that at least 60% of all coffee species are threatened with extinction.

The impacts of a changing climate on coffee-growing regions in South America, including Colombia, have been studied in a small number of publications. Only one study used CORDEX data, from the South American CORDEX domain (SAM-CORDEX). No studies are known that used the CAM-CORDEX simulations to study climate impacts on coffee crops in Colombia.

Fernandez et al. (2017) studied changes in climate over South America using projections made with a single RCM over the SAM-CORDEX domain. The Koppen–Trewartha classification (Trewartha and Horn, 1980) was used to identify six different climatic regimes, based on a combination of monthly, seasonal and annual averages of surface air temperature and precipitation. For Colombia, the projected changes in coffee-growing areas were a change from a sub-tropical humid climate to (mostly) tropical humid (rain forest). Smaller areas were projected to change to a tropical wet-dry (savannah-like) climate.

Ovalle-Rivera et al. (2015a) studied the impact of climate change on the suitability of areas for growing Arabica coffee worldwide. They used the “MaxEnt” algorithm (Philips et al. 2006) to predict areas for coffee crops and how they might change in the future. Climate change factors from 21 CMIP5 GCMs were added to climate data at 1 arc-second resolution (~1 km) from WorldClim (Hijmans et al. 2005) to create data for future time periods. In Colombia, the areas suitable for growing coffee could decrease by 16% (average), with an uncertainty range of -61% to +21%. The range of elevations suitable for Arabica coffee in the Andes was predicted to move upwards, from 500–1500 m in the present-day climate to 1000–2800 m in a future climate. Areas below 1800 m would become less suitable, but Colombia could gain some suitable areas at higher elevations.

Imbach et al. (2017) studied the effects of climate change on areas suitable for growing coffee, also using the MaxEnt algorithm, together with the impacts on numbers of bee species and populations in coffee-growing areas. Coffee production is dependent on bee pollination. WorldClim data were used to describe the present-day climate, and climate change factors from 19 CMIP5 climate models were combined with the WorldClim data to produce projections of future climate. In Colombia, bee populations were projected to fall in areas which could become suitable for growing coffee in a future climate; elsewhere, both bee populations and areas suitable for coffee would decline.

In contrast to many of the studies above, it has been suggested that coffee crops could be more resilient to climate change effects than was previously thought (DaMatta et al. 2019). Rising levels of carbon dioxide may result in increased yields and a better endurance of coffee plants against drought stress. However, considerable uncertainties remain on the effects of rising temperatures and carbon dioxide, and the prevalence of pests.

7.3. PRODUCTION OF DAILY CLIMATIC DATA SERIES

In this section, the production of daily data series for crop modelling in Colombia is summarised. Areas where coffee is grown were identified using data from the study by Monfreda et al. (2008; see Annex B, section B.3). One data type from this study is the fraction of a ~1 km area in which coffee crops are grown. These fractional areas were aggregated to the same resolution (0.25°, about 30 km) used by AgMERRA. Grid boxes with fractions above 0.004 corresponded reasonably closely to the coffee-growing areas shown in Figure 7-1. Time series of the key climatic variables for each of these grid boxes can be generated for driving the crop models.

The CAM-CORDEX RCMs have biases in temperature, rainfall and other variables (section 6.2). The decision was made to use 'delta-change' methods (Annex B) to calibrate the RCM data. Briefly, climate change factors calculated from the RCM simulations are combined with the AgMERRA data to produce meteorological data for the future time periods. The AgMERRA dataset (section 3.2) is used to represent baseline climatic conditions. AgMERRA contains daily values of the following meteorological variables for the period 1980-2010:

- Minimum and maximum temperature (°C)
- Precipitation (mm / day)
- Solar Radiation (MJ / m² / day)
- Relative humidity at time of maximum temperature (%)
- Surface wind speed (m / s)

Two different calibration methods were employed. Scaled distribution mapping (SDM; Switanek et al. 2017) was used to correct temperatures and precipitation amounts. SDM is based on quantile mapping, but accounts for the frequency of rain days and the likelihood of individual events more explicitly. The SDM method also preserves the projected changes and trends in meteorological variables. Currently, SDM has only been implemented for temperature and precipitation, as it assumes the distributions of these two variables can be described by particular functions. The distributions of other climatic variables would require alternative functions.

The remaining variables (humidity, surface wind speed and surface solar radiation) were corrected using a method based on simple ratio scaling (Haddeland et al. 2012). Ratios (*R*) of monthly mean values for the future and baseline periods for each variable were calculated as shown in Annex B. The observed (daily) values were then multiplied by the ratio for that month.

In the present study, a modified version of ratio scaling was used. In order to avoid discontinuities between months, daily weighting factors were calculated, following Hempel et al. (2013). First, for a given month, a daily index *d* is calculated from the day of the month *i* and the number of days in that month, *n*:

$$d = \frac{i-1}{n-1} - 0.5$$

Next, weighting factors are calculated for the previous month (subscript -), current month (subscript m) and following month (subscript +) from *d*:

$$d_- = 0.5 \times (|d| - d)$$

$$d_m = 1 - |d|$$

$$d_+ = 0.5 \times (|d| + d)$$

The weighted sum of the ratios for the previous, current and following months (R_- , R_m and R_+ respectively) is then calculated for each day of the present month:

$$R_i = d_-R_- + d_mR_m + d_+R_+$$

Finally, the calibrated values for day i in month m ($V_{i,m}^{calib}$) are obtained by multiplying the observed values ($O_{i,m}$) by R_i :

$$V_{i,m}^{calib} = O_{i,m} \times R_i$$

The same correction is applied to day i of month m in all years of the observed data.

Here, the baseline is defined as 1981-2000. Data from AgMERRA and the historical climate simulations for this period were used to calibrate climate data for 2021-2040 and 2041-2060.

8. SUMMARY

Seasonal forecasts from three different models have been evaluated globally, and over Europe and Colombia. Good skill for temperature was seen in all areas, although skill was low over a small area of northern Europe in all three models, suggesting a particular process is either missing or poorly represented in the models. Model skill for precipitation was notably poorer.

A subset of the higher resolution EURO-CORDEX simulations was assessed for the Mediterranean region, including a more detailed analysis over the MED-GOLD study regions. The models reproduced the observed spatial patterns and seasonal cycles, but biases were evident in the simulations. A quantile-based calibration method was applied to the model data, and greatly reduced the magnitudes of the biases.

A similar assessment was made of a subset of the RCM simulations in the CAM-CORDEX ensemble for Colombia. Here, the biases in the RCM simulations were larger than those over Europe, which partly originate in the driving GCMs; previous studies (not part of MED-GOLD) noted that large biases were evident in the GCMs over Colombia. For these reasons, an alternative calibration method (“delta-change”) was used.

The calibrated data for both Europe and Colombia can be used further for development and testing of the climate service tools in WPs 2, 3 and 4. Projections of basic meteorological variables and key climatic indices for each of the three crop types could also be used to assess the impacts of climate change, and drive crop models to provide further insights.

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ANNEX A. CORDEX SIMULATIONS

Global climate models (GCMs) provide projections of how the climate of the Earth may change in the future. However, the impacts of a changing climate, and the adaptation strategies required to deal with them, will occur on more regional (i.e. localised) spatial scales. Regional climate models (RCMs) provide climate projections with more accurate representations of local climate and extreme events, by simulating climate over (approximately) continental scales. The Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) was set up to provide regional climate projections for all land areas of the Earth, called domains. In this context, a domain is a region for which the regional climate simulations are available. Fourteen separate domains exist under CORDEX, of which three are relevant for MED-GOLD: EURO-CORDEX (which covers all of Europe), Med-CORDEX (which includes the southern half of Europe and northern Africa, and is centred on the Mediterranean Sea) and CAM-CORDEX (which covers Mexico, Latin America, and the northern part of South America). Simulations for the EURO- and Med-CORDEX domains are available at two resolutions: 0.44° (about 50 km) and a higher resolution of 0.11° (about 12 km). For the CAM-CORDEX domain, simulations are only available at 0.44°. Simulations using these three domains are discussed further in sections A.1 and A.2.

Regional climate models, by their nature, require climate information at the boundaries of their domains, which may come from either a reanalysis or a global climate model. Under CORDEX, a number of different RCMs are driven using climate information from a range of GCMs. The numbers of simulations, and combinations of RCMs and GCMs varies considerably between domains. The largest numbers of simulations are available for the EURO-CORDEX domain. For CAM-CORDEX, simulations are only available from two RCMs.

All of the CORDEX simulations fall under three main groups defined by the source of boundary climate information:

evaluation, where the regional climate models were driven by the ERA-Interim reanalysis (Dee et al. 2011). These simulations are used to assess how well models reproduce the observed climate.

historical simulations, where the RCMs are driven by GCMs that in turn were integrated using observed greenhouse gas concentrations, aerosol levels and land use change. A typical period would be 1950 to 2005.

projections of future climate under one or more scenarios of greenhouse gas emissions. Once again, the RCMs are driven using simulated climate information from GCMs. The future scenarios used within CORDEX are representative concentration pathways (RCPs). The most commonly studied scenarios are RCP4.5 (where the climate stabilises at about 3°C above pre-industrial temperatures) and RCP8.5 (which assumes large emissions of greenhouse gases and has correspondingly higher temperature increases). The projections are available for 2005 – 2100.

This annex shows the spatial extent of the three RCM domains (EURO-CORDEX, Med-CORDEX and CAM-CORDEX). Previously published studies evaluating the simulations of present-day climate and projected changes in climate using these three CORDEX domains (where available and relevant for MED-GOLD) are summarised. A number of studies have analysed simulations from both EURO-CORDEX and Med-CORDEX, so these two sets of simulations are summarised together.

A.1. EURO- AND MED-CORDEX

The EURO-CORDEX and Med-CORDEX domains are shown in Figure A-1. The EURO-CORDEX domain includes all of Europe, the Mediterranean Sea and the coastal regions of North Africa. The Med-CORDEX domain is smaller than the EURO-CORDEX domain, and the northern edge is located further south. This has the effect of placing the Mediterranean Sea and surrounding land areas in or close to the middle of the domain. A selection of studies whose analyses are relevant for MED-GOLD are divided into three groups and summarised in the following sections. It is not the intention to provide an exhaustive list and description of all publications which have used either or both of the EURO- and Med-CORDEX simulations.

A list of all GCM-RCM pairs used under EURO-CORDEX is available at:

<https://www.euro-cordex.net/060376/index.php.en>

In this report (section 5.), only EURO-CORDEX simulations were evaluated. There are fewer high-resolution simulations available from Med-CORDEX, and recently an issue was detected in one of the simulations, leading the provider to advise against its use (see: https://www.medcordex.eu/warnings/Communication-Issue-Files_CNRM-CM5_historical_6hLev_en.pdf). To keep the analysis focused, it was decided to analyse simulations from EURO-CORDEX only. However, it is expected that any analyses using the Med-CORDEX simulations would produce similar results, as shown by the studies summarised in sections A.1.1-A.1.3.

Figure A-1: EURO-CORDEX model domain (left panel) and Med-CORDEX domain (right panel).

A.1.1. EVALUATION OF BENEFITS OF HIGH RESOLUTION SIMULATIONS

A small number of studies have explicitly evaluated the benefits of simulations of climate using models at two or more spatial resolutions. Simulations made with GCMs (whose resolutions are approximately 100-200 km) have been compared with those by RCMs (resolutions of 0.44°; about 50 km). Additionally, higher-resolution RCM simulations (0.11°; about 12 km) have been compared with the lower resolution RCM runs (0.44°).

Torma et al. (2015) and Prein et al. (2016) studied modelled precipitation over the Alps in the EURO- and Med-CORDEX simulations. They compared the RCM simulations at 0.11° and 0.44° with the simulations by the driving GCMs and observed precipitation amounts. The RCM simulations at both resolutions were a clear improvement over the GCMs, and the simulations at 0.11° were closer to the observations than those at 0.44°. The improvements at higher resolutions came from better representation of the complex orography in the Alps. The provenance of the added value is therefore related to physical processes within the RCMs, and not to a disaggregation of the large-scale forcing.

Casanueva et al. (2016) studied daily precipitation totals in EURO-CORDEX RCMs driven by ERA-Interim, focusing on Spain and the Alps. Simulations at both resolutions (0.11° and 0.44°) were examined. The modelled data were compared with two gridded datasets derived from high density networks of surface rain gauges, Spain011/044 and EURO4M-APGD for the Alpine region. They found only limited evidence for added value of the higher resolution simulations for the precipitation intensity and frequency.

Soares and Cardoso (2018) assessed the added value of higher-resolution RCM simulations of daily precipitation, by comparing EURO-CORDEX simulations at resolutions of 0.11° and 0.44° with ERA-Interim (resolution about 0.70°). The simulations with RCMs at both resolutions showed an improvement over ERA-Interim, but evidence for further improvement of the 0.11° simulations over those at 0.44° was more limited. In the latter case, most of the improvement was in areas where convection is important (for example, the Alps, Iberia). Three RCMs showed a large increase in accuracy when run at 0.11° resolution, but there was no real gain for other RCMs (i.e. when comparing 0.11° and 0.44° simulations).

A.1.2. EVALUATIONS OF EURO- AND MED-CORDEX

In this section, studies evaluating simulations from EURO- and Med-CORDEX are summarised, where relevant for MED-GOLD. Most studies focused on simulations of precipitation or temperatures. No studies assessing simulations of humidity and surface wind speeds are known.

Jacob et al. (2014) evaluated eleven EURO-CORDEX simulations, focusing on mean temperatures and precipitation, numbers of very wet days, dry spell lengths, and numbers of heat waves for the entire model domain. The tabulated values of a range of impact variables averaged over EU sub-regions for baseline and 2071-2100 were given.

Kotlarski et al. (2014) evaluated monthly and seasonal values of air temperature and precipitation in the ERA-Interim driven EURO-CORDEX simulations, using E-OBS data for 1989-2008. They found no added value in the RCM simulations at increased spatial resolution when the data were aggregated into seasonal mean quantities over large European subdomains.

Dell'Aquila et al. (2018) studied decadal variability in the Med-CORDEX simulations, focusing on temperature and precipitation in the ERA-Interim driven simulations, focusing on those run at 0.44° (50 km) resolution. They used gridded observations from the CRU TS3 v22 dataset, at 0.5° resolution (Harris et al. 2014). The Med-CORDEX simulations generally underestimated the observed (positive) trend in surface air temperature, especially in the summer season. The representation of the time series of precipitation, averaged over the Mediterranean, was satisfactory.

Cardoso et al. (2019) evaluated mean and extreme daily temperatures in Portugal from the EURO-CORDEX simulations, using temperatures from 42 weather stations for the period 1971-2000. They also studied projections of mean and extreme temperatures for 2071-2100. Maximum temperatures during the warm season (May to September) were projected to exceed the historical 90th percentile more than 50% of the time. On average, 60 tropical nights, when daily minimum temperatures remain above 20°C, were projected for the end of the century; there are only 7 tropical nights in the historical period. Heat waves were projected to become warmer, more frequent and affect larger areas of Portugal.

Fantini et al. (2018) assessed multiple daily precipitation statistics in the ERA-Interim driven Med-CORDEX and EURO-CORDEX simulations (mean precipitation, distributions of daily precipitation amounts, dry spell lengths and numbers of very wet days). The RCMs were evaluated using high-resolution gridded datasets produced for specific countries or regions (e.g., Spain02; CETEMPS for Italy). An evaluation was not made for Portugal, as a high resolution gridded precipitation dataset for Portugal did not exist at the time of writing. Overall, the performance of RCM simulations in Med-CORDEX and EURO-CORDEX was of similar quality over the Mediterranean regions.

Mascaro et al. (2018) evaluated annual and seasonal mean precipitation in EURO-CORDEX over Sardinia, using 0.11° and 0.44° resolutions. They used a high-density rain gauge network to evaluate the models. The simulated spatial patterns of climatological annual and seasonal means agreed well with the observations at both resolutions, but the models overestimated the spatial variability. This study is particularly useful as it focuses on a small region (i.e. very small compared with the size of the RCM domain), as will be necessary for the MED-GOLD study areas.

A.1.3. CLIMATE PROJECTIONS USING EURO- AND MED-CORDEX

In this section, studies evaluating projections of future climate from the EURO- and Med-CORDEX simulations are assessed. As before, most studies have focused on temperature and rainfall, as weather station observations and high resolution gridded data are available for these two variables. Only one study has assessed simulated surface solar radiation fluxes.

Fernández et al. (2018) studied projections of several ensembles of RCMs, including Med- and EURO-CORDEX, over Spain and Portugal. They showed that some of the local details produced by the RCMs are inconsistent with the driving GCM. For example, the CLM RCM simulated large increases in precipitation over the western Mediterranean Sea during summer when driven by two different GCMs. However, a drying over the same region was projected by one of the GCMs. Fernández et al. (2018) make the point that this increase in summer precipitation could be interpreted either as added value of the dynamical downscaling, or as a specific bias of this RCM. They also note that only a small number of GCMs have been downscaled by multiple RCMs, and that only a few RCMs have been driven by many GCMs. Consequently, the projections in EURO- and Med-CORDEX are biased towards certain GCMs and RCMs.

Santos et al. (2018a) studied the thermal growing conditions of 44 grape cultivars in Portugal. Daily temperatures from E-OBS were downscaled from 25 km to 1 km using elevation, distance to coast and latitude. Growing degree hours (GDH) were calculated using a cosine function between two fixed temperatures. Projections from four GCM-RCM pairs from EURO-CORDEX were used to calculate climate change factors that were added to the observed temperatures. An increase in GDH was projected over all of Portugal for the period 2041-2070, but the largest increases and subsequent impacts were projected over the north of the country. The climatic conditions under which one class of cultivars are presently grown was projected to disappear entirely.

Santos et al. (2018b) evaluated changes in extreme precipitation over Portugal using seven GCM-RCM pairs of the 0.11° simulations from EURO-CORDEX, which were driven by the RCP8.5 scenario. Eight different precipitation indices were used in the assessment. Significant drying trends were projected in spring, mainly over northern and central Portugal, while weak wetting trends were detected in autumn. Large increases in consecutive dry days over Portugal were projected, especially in the south of the country. The proportion of precipitation falling as extremes was projected to increase, particularly in the south.

Bartók et al. (2017) compared projections of surface solar radiation (SSR) simulated by four EURO-CORDEX regional climate models (CCLM, RCA4, WRF, ALADIN) with the respective fields of their ten driving CMIP5 global climate models. Data from the World Radiation Data Centre (25 stations in Europe) were used to evaluate models. In absolute terms, all models underestimated cloudiness and overestimated SSR. The analysis of projected changes in SSR focused on seasonal and annual totals. Bartók et al. (2017) found that the GCMs projected an increase in SSR over Europe, whereas the RCMs projected a decrease. The largest differences appeared in spring and summer. The cause was the different changes in cloudiness; cloudiness was projected to decline in the GCM simulations, but no discernible change was seen in the RCM simulations.

A.2. CAM-CORDEX SIMULATIONS

The CAM-CORDEX domain is centred on the Equator, and includes Latin America, the northern half of South America, and Mexico (Figure A-2). The border of Colombia is shown, indicating that Colombia is located near the middle of the domain.

Figure A-2: The CAM-CORDEX domain. The border of Colombia is also shown.

Very few studies using climate data from the CAM-CORDEX simulations have been published that include results for Colombia. The majority of the published studies have focused on analyses of temperature and precipitation over Central America and Mexico. Diro et al. (2014) studied tropical cyclones in ERA-Interim and GCM-driven RCM simulations from CAM-CORDEX, focusing on a single RCM. They used six hourly best-track data and other information such as the central location of named TCs, the associated maximum wind speed and sea level pressure from the Tropical Prediction Centre/National Hurricane Centre of the USA. The frequency of tropical cyclones was projected to decrease in the Atlantic and coastal regions of the Pacific but increase over the western areas of the East Pacific.

ANNEX B. CALIBRATION OF CLIMATE MODEL DATA

B.1. INTRODUCTION

Although climate models replicate many observed features of the climate system, simulations of present-day climate do not precisely match observations. A comparison of climate model simulations with observations is likely to show some differences, for which there are a variety of reasons. Our understanding of physical processes within the climate system is constantly improving but remains incomplete. Other factors that contribute to the differences are the representation of climate processes within models, uncertain historical forcing, and imperfect initialization of climate models. Climatic variations occur on a wide range of spatial and temporal scales, some of which will not be resolved by a climate model. Simplifications often need to be made when representing climatic processes within climate models. All of these factors lead to systematic differences between model simulations and observations, which are collectively called “model bias” or simply “bias”. Even a perfect model (at a given resolution) would exhibit differences in climate from that measured at a weather station.

It is desirable to reduce the size of the bias in climate model data prior to its use, a process referred to as “calibration” in this report (other terms often used are “bias adjustment” or “bias correction”). Calibration is important and necessary, as many of the crop models and indices are based on absolute values of climatic variables. A wide range of calibration methods have been published and used within the scientific literature. Some methods have been described and compared by Hawkins et al. (2013), Räisänen and Rätty (2013) and Maraun (2016). These methods range from simple addition of or multiplication by correction factors to more sophisticated statistical methods (Maraun, 2016; Galmarini et al. 2019). Traditionally, most attention has been focused on adjustment of temperature and precipitation. Adjustment of other meteorological variables has only received limited attention.

Regardless of their complexity, all calibration methods fall into one of two types, “delta-change” or “shift” (section B.2). Under the delta-change approach, climate change factors are calculated using modelled data for the present-day (or “baseline”) and a future time period, and are applied to an observed series of data. The shift method calculates correction factors using observed and modelled data for a common time period. These correction factors are then applied to modelled data in both the baseline and future time periods. These correction factors have been generally been applied on daily and monthly timescales, and also to individual quantiles.

There are often pragmatic reasons for choosing a particular calibration method. The availability of observations and the underlying terrain of the region of interest can also be deciding factors. If the terrain is fairly flat and uniform, and the density of observations is high, a simple “shift” method could be used. In areas with fewer observations and/or complex terrain, the delta-change method might be more suitable.

Some calibration methods, especially those correcting precipitation, are complex, as both the precipitation amounts and numbers of wet and dry days need to be calibrated. Translating the relevant equations from a scientific article or technical document into a computer program and testing it is non-trivial and can be time consuming. The availability of an existing computer program implementing a particular calibration method in a language a researcher is familiar with can be a major factor in its use.

Calibration of climate model simulations can introduce its own problems. There is often no ‘correct’ or ‘best’ method, but some are probably better than others. Many calibration methods modify climate variables separately, which might lead to non-physical combinations. Calibration methods often correct one or a small number of aspects of the modelled data, such as the mean and variability.

No calibration method can overcome fundamental problems of a climate model simulation, such as underestimation of the persistence of blocking events which can lead to heat waves or prolonged cold spells. Despite these issues, reduction of biases in climate model simulations by use of a calibration method is necessary for MED-GOLD. In this Annex, a brief overview of calibration methods is given, together with their advantages and disadvantages. The calibration of climate data for Colombia, and production of daily data for driving crop models, is described in section 7.3.

B.2. BRIEF OVERVIEW OF CALIBRATION METHODS

There are a wide variety of methods for calibration of climate model data, ranging from simple addition of or multiplication by correction factors, to more sophisticated statistical methods. Traditionally, most attention has been focused on calibration of temperature and precipitation. Calibration of other meteorological variables has only received limited attention.

The calibration method chosen may be due to pragmatic reasons as well as its performance. Some methods, especially those correcting precipitation amounts, can be complex, as the numbers of dry and wet days is often calibrated, as well as the actual precipitation totals. Translating the calibration equations from a scientific article or technical document into a computer program and testing it is non-trivial and can be time consuming. The availability of

an existing computer program implementing a given calibration method in a language a researcher is familiar with is often a major factor in the choice of method.

Most calibration methods, regardless of their complexity, fall into one of two groups, which can be termed “delta-change” and “shift”. The simplest forms of these two methods are summarised below together with some of their advantages and disadvantages. When calibrating climate data, it is common to refer to the time period of the observations as the “baseline”.

B.2.1. DELTA-CHANGE

The “delta-change” calibration method is the most commonly used, and is conceptually the simplest. Climate change factors, which are the differences in a variable of interest between a future time period and the baseline, are added to the observations. For example, the mean difference in temperature between a future period (T_{fut}) and a baseline (T_{base}) are calculated and added to the observed values, as shown in equation (5). The overbars indicate averages over the future and baseline time periods. These averages are usually monthly values, but can also be daily values. T_{calib} and T_{obs} are calibrated and observed daily temperatures respectively.

$$T_{calib} = T_{obs} + (\bar{T}_{fut} - \bar{T}_{base}) \quad (5)$$

Several other calibration methods also fall under this definition. Quantile mapping, as described by Amengual et al. (2012), involves the calculation of change factors for individual quantiles which are added to the quantiles of the observations. Scaled distribution mapping (Switanek et al. 2017) also adds correction factors to observed quantiles, but uses a different approach for their calculation.

Some meteorological variables have a lower limit; for example, relative humidity and precipitation cannot have values less than zero. Addition of a climate change factor, as shown in equation (5), is therefore not appropriate. For these types of variables, ratio scaling (sometimes called simple ratio scaling) was used (Haddeland et al. 2012). The ratio of modelled data for the future and baseline periods is calculated, and the observed values are multiplied by this ratio, as shown in equation (6). As before, the overbars represent climatological averages over a time period, usually monthly means. P_{calib} and P_{obs} represent calibrated and observed daily precipitation totals respectively. The size of the ratio is sometimes limited to avoid excessive upscaling or reduction of the observed values.

$$P_{calib} = P_{obs} \times \frac{\bar{P}_{fut}}{\bar{P}_{base}} \quad (6)$$

Advantages

- Calibrated data are based on observed daily series, which contains real events.
- Calibrated data are representative of the site of interest.
- Some model errors will cancel out.

Disadvantages

- Corrected data resemble the observed series, because the climate change factors tend to be small compared with the observed values.
- Any modelled changes in frequencies of climatic events (e.g. droughts, wet spells) will not be carried through to the corrected data.
- Corrected data are not continuous between different future time periods.

B.2.2. SHIFT

Under the shift method, observations and climate model data over a common time period are used to calculate correction factors, which are then applied to the climate model data in all time periods (equation (7)). Here, T_{calib} represents the calibrated daily temperatures and T_{model} the raw (i.e. uncorrected) modelled daily temperatures. T_{model} represents temperatures for any time period. The third and fourth terms inside the brackets in equation (2) represent

mean observed and modelled temperatures respectively for the baseline period. As before, these terms could be daily or monthly mean values.

$$T_{calib} = T_{model} + \left(\overline{T_{obs}^{base}} - \overline{T_{model}^{base}} \right) \quad (7)$$

Advantages

- Creates a continuous series of corrected model data.
- Any modelled changes in frequencies of climatic events (e.g. droughts, wet spells) will be carried through to the calibrated data.

Disadvantages

- Assumes the modelled biases remain constant, which may not be correct.
- Some errors in modelled data, e.g., numbers of wet and dry days, under- or over-estimation of lengths of warm spells, will still be present.
- Modelled data may not represent climate of location of interest accurately, especially in areas with complex terrain and/or sparse observations.

B.3. CALIBRATION ALGORITHMS USED IN THIS STUDY

Seasonal forecasts were calibrated using the variance inflation method described by Torralba et al. (2017), who used it to produce reliable seasonal predictions of wind speeds. This calibration strategy was selected because it can be considered as a way of obtaining predictions with an interannual variance equivalent to that of a reference dataset, but at the same time ensuring an increased reliability of the probability predictions.

Empirical quantile mapping (EQM) was used to calibrate climate data from the EURO-CORDEX simulations (section 5.). Briefly, this method consists of calibrating the simulated cumulative distribution function (CDF) by adding to the observed quantiles both the mean delta change and the individual delta changes in the corresponding quantiles. An analytical description of the method can be found in Gutiérrez et al. (2019) and Ituribe et al. (2019). EQM is implemented in the “downscaleR” package in the R language, which is freely available from:

<https://github.com/SantanderMetGroup/downscaleR>

In addition, results are shown for the EQM calibration method for the reference period (1971-2000) by using the cross validation approach. Cross validation tests whether the relationship established between the predictor (RCMs) and predictand (E-OBS) remains valid outside the training period (Gutiérrez et al. 2019). In this report the available data (n = 30 years) are partitioned into k-non-overlapping “folds” or subsets, each containing n/k elements (k=5 1971:1976, 1977:1982, 1983:1988, 1989:1994 and 1995:2000). The EQM method is then calibrated and validated k times, considering in turn each of the folds as a test set and training the method with the remaining (k-1) sets. The resulting k-test series are typically joined and validated together in a single series spanning the whole analysis period. For more information on the cross validation approach the reader is referred to Gutiérrez et al. (2019).

A similar algorithm to EQM, scaled distribution mapping (SDM) algorithm has been implemented into the pyCAT package, which is available from:

<https://github.com/wegener-center/pyCAT>

For Colombia, SDM was used to calibrate temperatures and precipitation amounts. Simple ratio scaling was used to calibrate the remaining variables. An algorithm for the simple ratio scaling approach was written in-house. Technical issues meant it was not possible to use the downscaleR package to calibrate data for Colombia.

ANNEX C. EVALUATION OF EURO-CORDEX OVER ANDALUSIA

A five member RCM ensemble was evaluated over the Douro valley and Andalusia using data from E-OBS (section 5.2). Several different climatic indices based on temperature and precipitation (Table 5-2) were calculated using data from three sources: E-OBS, the raw model data, and the calibrated model data. In this annex, maps of Andalusia, southern Spain, showing the indices calculated from each of the three observed datasets are presented, together with statistical measures of the modelled performance. These results are particularly relevant for WP2, for the olive sector.

In all cases, standard climatological three-month seasons were used: winter – December, January and February (DJF); spring – March, April and May (MAM); summer – June, July and August (JJA); autumn – September, October and November (SON).

Figure C-3: Changes in seasonal mean Tx over Andalusia between 2031-2060 and 1971-2000 for the five member RCM ensemble, from both the calibrated simulations (ENS-EQM) and raw model output (ENS-RAW). Results are shown for the RCP4.5 scenario (top two rows) and RCP8.5 (middle two rows). The bottom row illustrates the same changes in the numbers of summer days (SU).

Figure C-4: As Figure C-3 but for the period 2071-2100.

Figure C-5: Changes in seasonal mean Tn over Andalusia between 2031-2060 and 1971-2000 for the five member RCM ensemble, from both the calibrated simulations (ENS-EQM) and raw model output (ENS-RAW). Results are shown for the RCP4.5 scenario (top two rows) and RCP8.5 (middle two rows). The bottom row illustrates the same changes in the numbers of tropical nights (TR).

Figure C-6: As Figure C-5 but for the period 2071-2100.

Figure C-7: Changes in the seasonal mean RR over Andalusia between the 2031-2060 and the 1971-2000 for the five member RCM ensemble, from both the calibrated simulations (ENS-EQM) and raw model output (ENS-RAW). Results are shown for the RCP4.5 scenario (top two rows) and RCP8.5 (middle two rows). Changes in the mean annual numbers of wet days (RR1) are shown in the bottom row.

Figure C-8: As Figure C-7 but for the 2071-2100 period.

ANNEX D. TECHNICAL INFORMATION

In this annex, sources of non-climate data are described. Calculations of other climatic and non-climatic variables are also summarised.

D.1. COFFEE CROP INFORMATION

Coffee growing areas worldwide were identified by Monfreda et al. (2008) using a wide variety of datasets. One product from this study was an estimation of the harvested area fraction (the fraction of a 10' grid box used for coffee plantations). This dataset was used to identify the grid boxes in AgMERRA within which coffee is grown. The data files were obtained from:

<http://www.earthstat.org/harvested-area-yield-175-crops/>

The particular dataset used is named "coffee_HarvestedAreaFraction". The data were aggregated to the 0.25° grid of AgMERRA using area-weighted averaging. Grid boxes with harvested areas greater than zero contained coffee crops.

Coffee production and export data for Colombia were obtained from the Federación Nacional de Cafeteros (National Federation of Coffee Growers of Colombia), FNC:

https://www.federaciondefcafeteros.org/particulares/en/quienes_somos/119_estadisticas_historicas/

Three data files were obtained that contained data on annual cultivated areas, monthly production volumes and monthly export volumes. These data are shown in section 7.1.

D.2. CALCULATION OF SURFACE ELEVATION IN AGMERRA

Coffee is grown at altitudes above 500 m in Colombia. The elevation (or altitude) of the AgMERRA data is not provided. However, the surface geopotential of the underlying MERRA reanalysis is available.

The surface geopotential was obtained from the site below:

https://iridl.ldeo.columbia.edu/SOURCES/.NASA/.GSFC/.MERRA/.Anl_Const_2D/

The surface elevation Z was calculated as follows. First, the surface geopotential height H is found from the geopotential by dividing by standard gravity, g_0 :

$$H = \text{geopotential} / g_0$$

where $g_0 = 9.80665 \text{ m s}^{-2}$.

Next, the surface elevation Z was calculated from the geopotential height:

$$Z = R \times H / R - H$$

where R is the radius of the Earth. For low elevations, Z and H will be almost identical.

D.3. ESTIMATION OF RELATIVE HUMIDITY AT TIME OF MAXIMUM TEMPERATURE

The AgMERRA dataset (Ruane et al. 2015) includes the relative humidity at the time of maximum temperature (RHT_{max}) for each day. This quantity was included instead of a daily mean or maximum relative humidity, as it can be converted to vapour pressure and dew point temperature because it corresponds with a specific temperature. RHT_{max} corresponds approximately to the time of peak evapotranspiration and minimum relative humidity. It also mimics the ~2 p.m. local time sling psychrometer observations that were often used to estimate vapour pressure deficits for crop model development (Ruane et al. 2015).

RHT_{max} is not available from the CORDEX simulations. Only daily mean relative humidity was archived, so RHT_{max} was estimated using the steps below. These steps implicitly assume that the actual vapour pressure of water remains approximately constant during the day. This assumption may be reasonable for a humid sub-tropical climate; a study using observations from Japan in an area with this type of climate noted that the dew point temperature remained relatively constant during the day (Gunawardhana et al. 2017).

Relative humidity can be calculated as the ratio of the vapour pressure of water present (e) and the saturation vapour pressure e_{sat} as shown in equation (1). The saturation vapour pressure, e_{sat} , is a function of temperature T (equation (2)), where T has units of Celsius. The constants A , B and C have values of: $A = 17.625$, $B = 243.04^{\circ}C$, and $C = 610.94$ Pa (Lawrence, 2005).

$$RH = \frac{e}{e_{sat}} \quad (1)$$

$$e_{sat} = C \times \exp\left(\frac{AT}{B+T}\right) \quad (2)$$

Relative humidity at the time of maximum temperature was estimated from the CAM-CORDEX model data as follows. First, daily mean temperatures of the CAM-CORDEX simulations were calculated as the average of the maximum and minimum temperatures, as shown in equation (3):

$$T_{mean} = \frac{T_{max} + T_{min}}{2} \quad (3)$$

The saturation vapour pressure e_{sat} was calculated from this daily mean temperature with equation (2), then the actual vapour pressure e was found from the daily mean relative humidity using equation (1). It is implicitly assumed that the vapour pressure (e) is approximately constant during the day (Andersson-Sköld et al. 2008). Next, the saturation vapour pressure at daily maximum temperature, $e_{sat}(T_{max})$, was calculated using equation (2). Finally, the relative humidity at maximum temperature (RHT_{max}) is calculated with equation (4) using the values of e and $e_{sat}(T_{max})$.

$$RHT_{max} = \frac{e}{e_{sat}(T_{max})} \quad (4)$$

D.4. EMISSIONS SCENARIOS

It is not possible to predict future emissions of greenhouse gases. Future emissions will depend on demand, energy mixes used (i.e. proportions of renewables and fossil-fuel based sources), the types of emissions reduction programs implemented by governments (if any), how quickly they would be implemented, and how effective they would be. For these reasons, projections of future climate use emissions scenarios. An emissions scenario is an estimate of future emissions based on understanding of natural sources of greenhouse gases and on assumptions about future socio-economic trends, that is, the amounts of greenhouse gases that could be released into the atmosphere by human activities.

It isn't clear exactly how global social and economic systems will respond to emissions reduction programs. A range of different emissions scenarios are used to describe possible future trends in emissions of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere, and hence a range of global temperature changes and impacts. The CMIP3 projections used the older SRES emissions scenarios (A1FI, A1B, A1T, A2, B1 and B2), whereas the latest sets of climate projections (CMIP5, CORDEX) use the newer representative concentration pathways (RCPs).

Figure D-9: Comparison of SRES and RCP emissions scenarios. (a) Radiative forcing; and (b) corresponding global mean temperature change (relative to the mean for 1986-2005).

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